

D4.1. Roadmap linking technical machine learning & statistical solutions with user needs

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIA	Artificial Intelligence Act
AUV	Aerial Unmanned Vehicles
BAT	Best Available Technology
BHD	Birds and Habitats Directives
BRT	Boosted Regression Trees
BSAP	Black Sea Against Pollution
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
CFP	Common Fisheries Policy
CNN	Convolutional Neural Networks
DL	Deep Learning
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DOME	Data, Optimization, Modelling and Evaluation
EBV	Essential Biodiversity Variables
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EO	Earth Observation
EOV	Essential Ocean Variables
ERDDAP	Environmental Research Division Data Access Programme
EU	European Union
EV	Essential Variables
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HELCOM	Helsinki Commission
iFDOs	image FAIR Digital Objects
jSDM	joint Species Distribution Models
LOOCV	Leaving One Out Cross-Validation
ML	Machine Learning
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NRL	Nature Restoration Law
OBAMA-NEXT	Observing and Mapping Marine Ecosystems-Next Generation Tools
ODV	Ocean Data View
OSPAR	Oslo and Paris Convention
PAB	Practitioners Advisory Board
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PDS	Planetary Data System
PL	Plackett-Luce
ROV	Remotely Operated Vehicle
RSCs	Regional Seas Conventions
SDM	Species Distribution Models
SfM	Structure from Motion
THREDDS	Thematic Real-time Environmental Distributed Data Services
TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability, and Technology
UNSDG	United Nations Sustainable Development Goals
WDS	World Data System
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WP	Work Package

1. Executive summary

The European Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA) defines an Artificial Intelligence (AI) system as software that is developed for a given set of human-defined objectives, generating outputs such as content, predictions, recommendations, or decisions. The AIA also aims to have an open definition of an AI system that is future-proof and includes wider domains usually considered outside of the realm of AI including statistical approaches. Therefore, this report focusses on the application of machine learning and statistical approaches in biodiversity research (e.g. species identification and mapping). The objective of these guidelines is to describe reliable computing solutions that address biodiversity relevant policy needs.

The OBAMA-NEXT project relies on four types of data: genetic data, remote sensing data, imaging data and heterogeneous data for hybrid approaches. The aim of the project is to make new data and digital resources available under FAIR, CARE and TRUST principles. The FAIR principle aims to ensure that digital resources are useful and manageable by making them accessible, interoperable and reusable for both humans and computers. This implies to share code development through platforms such as GitHub, and publishing data and codes in repositories such as Zenodo with DOIs that can be easily referenced in the scientific publications describing them. While the FAIR principle focuses more on the identification and operability of data, the CARE principle seeks to ensure the rights of data and code providers, while the TRUST principle focuses on ensuring that the digital repositories are trustworthy.

The production of trustworthy and reliable systems requires appropriate validation and testing procedures. Such systems development is not just building a model but it consists of several steps of data pre-processing and modelling in a pipeline. Therefore, for an appropriate assessment of a given system's performance all the processes in the pipeline must be validated together, not only the model standalone. Each data splitting in training and testing techniques have their own statistical properties, where several should be considered obsolete, despite often still used. Among the techniques, repeated stratified cross-validation and bootstrapping emerge as the most robust. Finally, biased training data and over confidence on expert knowledge are likely the main issues when statistically-tested models underperform in real environment final operationalization. Several examples are provided where these issues are addressed by comparing the systems with alternative related data (ground truth).

The final chapter revises the main international and EU biodiversity policy frameworks highlighted under the OBAMA-NEXT stakeholder consultation process where PAB members identified principal policy implementation processes to be addressed in relation to AI helping to address specific biodiversity data needs. Furthermore, some examples of recent research and application addressing these needs are provided. Most of these policies refer to the need of monitoring aided by new technologies, which would include AI approaches. However, there are sparse policies making explicit reference to AI (e.g. the Common Fisheries Policy -CFP- and the Green Deal). The Marine Strategy Framework Directive, the Regional Seas Conventions and the CFP are where more examples of AI application can likely be found in the literature (e.g. species identifications by image analysis, automatization of monitoring of the marine environment, identifying links between human activities, pressures and ecosystem state components, and commercial fish stock assessments).

2. Introduction to trustworthy artificial intelligence

The European Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA), in Article 3 point 1, **defines an Artificial Intelligence (AI) system as “software that is developed with one or more of the techniques and approaches listed in Annex I and can, for a given set of human-defined objectives, generate outputs such as content, predictions, recommendations, or decisions influencing the environments they interact with”**. The AI techniques and approaches listed in Annex I are classified in three groups (Figure 1):

- Machine Learning (ML)** approaches, including supervised, unsupervised and reinforcement learning, using a wide variety of methods including Deep Learning (DL).
- Logic- and knowledge-based approaches**, including knowledge representation, inductive (logic) programming, knowledge bases, inference and deductive engines, (symbolic) reasoning and expert systems.
- Statistical approaches**, Bayesian estimation, search and optimization methods.

Figure 1. Classification of Artificial Intelligence techniques and approaches in the Artificial Intelligence Act proposal, expanded with further subcategories commonly used in marine sciences (reproduced from Fernandes-Salvador et al., 2022).

While (a) and (b) groups refer to specific fields within AI in computer science, group (c) includes generic fields that are usually considered outside AI or part of their mathematical or statistical foundation. In the case of statistics, they represent a mathematical science on its own, with the aim of having an open definition of AI system that is future-proof, this classification is neither exhaustive nor exclusive. Some specific techniques and approaches may not be explicitly listed, whereas others can belong to more than one group (e.g. Bayesian ML approaches). However, these approaches can be prone to the same biases and issues that machine learning has.

Actually, the recommendations in these guidelines were developed originally in the statistical and mathematical domain to avoid overfitting and for fair comparison of methods (e.g. when comparing simpler and more complex models). For example, non-parametric statistical modelling can be prone to overfitting like many machine learning approaches. It must be also considered that apparently simple mathematical models might have a complex data processing beforehand, which needs to be also assessed together with the model.

Deploying AI in marine biodiversity research bears various opportunities; however, precautionary measures must be undertaken to avoid undermining the trust of stakeholders, such as policy implementation managers, scientists and fishers, in terms of AI's capacity to provide accurate products (Sohns et al., 2022). Privacy issues and ethical concerns of end-users and data providers need to be seriously considered, such as for instance when dealing with video surveillance on-board vessels or other public or private facilities. Data use should be communicated beforehand, and permissions renewed if additional use within ethical boundaries and legislation is desired, especially if human images or behaviours can be identified or inferred. Lack of transparency regarding the extent of data use could greatly decrease trust in ML applications. Additional concerns exist around biases in training data and algorithms leading to predictive profiling (Probst, 2020; Lekunberri et al., 2022). Practitioners should be aware of potential pitfalls regarding domain shifts, in which discrepancies arise between the context from where data is used to train models versus the context where models are deployed, leading to unintended extrapolation of algorithms. The often misconceived perception of all ML being a black box, could lead to distrust of its usefulness by stakeholders in important biodiversity policy choices such as stock quotas and management rules (Sohns et al., 2022).

When using confidential data, e.g. georeferenced data that allow for identifying individual activity's locations, scientists typically aggregate analysis steps to cautiously anonymise results. Often, this is done manually before any statistical model is applied. The introduction of deep learning methods, working best on raw, disaggregated data, however, bears the risk of breaching confidential information. Even if ML practitioners guard against a negligent breach, confidential information can still be inferred via a malicious attack on the trained model. The flow of information in a ML model is not one-way, but can be turned the other way, reconstructing the raw training data or some subset from a trained model, called model inversion (Veale et al., 2018). The possibility of model inversion and membership inference attacks, the latter seeking to identify an individual as part of the training set, suggests that some models themselves may warrant considerations as confidential data. This finding has implications for reporting results, the ever-growing open accessibility of models, and the possibility for new users to openly apply existing models with their own data.

While the use of ML approaches in biological sciences has grown exponentially, with over 8,000 peer reviewed scientific publications in 2020 alone (Walsh et al., 2023), its use in marine biodiversity monitoring has so far remained limited, as stated in OBAMA-NEXT Milestone 1.2 "Report on survey to Practitioners Advisory Board (PAB)", and included in Deliverable 1.1 (Borja et al., 2023). Some examples include ML for seagrass or kelp mapping (Duffy et al., 2019; Marquez et al., 2022), benthic communities (Gauci et al., 2016; Mohamed et al., 2018) or mammal and fish species identification, based on the acoustic patterns (Silva et al., 2022; Nur Korkmaz et al.,

2023; Barroso et al., 2023). Hence, PAB members are considering incorporating monitoring tools (including tools based on AI) with expectations of repeatability throughout time and space; to be reasonably affordable for operating and maintaining; able to work autonomously for a long time-period; easy to use, easy to process large data sets; be cost-effective (reasonably affordable), non-invasive and scalable (Borja et al., 2023). The major obstacles in biodiversity monitoring indicated by PAB members are a lack of budget, a lack of coordination and inappropriate spatial resolution of data as well as a lack of tools and standardization (Borja et al., 2023). They indicated pertinent data gaps were also: numerical data for species, communities, and habitats, data on temporal dynamics (species and communities) and spatial distribution (for species and habitats). They do not need categorical data and categorical expert judgement data. Most of them have confidence measures associated with their data, and mostly quantitative. AI can help to address these needs providing huge amounts of data not possible with traditional methods, but requires a large initial investment in people training, development and testing. These guidelines aim to provide advice that can reduce this investment. These guidelines also aim to be useful for the PAB and ICES by increasing cooperation through the WGMLEARN group and other European projects in order to contribute to the harmonization of monitoring methods across Europe.

In this context, **the objective of this OBAMA-NEXT Deliverable 4.1 is to build a guideline for trustworthy and reliable AI solutions addressing user needs considering current legislation.** Therefore, types of data addressed in the project are first reviewed, then current FAIR, CARE and TRUST principles are described, and finally methodologies for trustful AI solutions development are summarised. For completing this, the project has Task 4.1, which tries to define processing chains for generating technical solutions to achieve information products (identified in WP1), including data flow, data pre-processing, algorithm and model selection, and data product definitions. Since these should be open access, the definitions of these are included in Section 3 of this deliverable. Also, Task 4.1 aims to determine the limitations and applicability of these methods depending on data and their quality, in relation to the intended products to be developed, as described in Deliverable 1.1 (Borja et al., 2023). This has been included in Section 4. Later, Task 4.1 defines agreed-upon protocols and methods for training, testing and validating core AI modules (e.g., validation schemes, validation metrics and statistical tests). Hence, good AI practices and protocols for validation against ground truth independent data are established, as shown in Section 5. Finally, a review of current European legislation and policies, and their potential AI needs and alignment is included in Section 6, linked also to Deliverable 6.1 (Walton et al., 2023), as a basis for a roadmap in the use of AI in marine biodiversity monitoring.

3. Types of biodiversity data generated within OBAMA-NEXT

These guidelines provide wide-encompassing advice on how to implement trustworthy AI solutions for multiple types of data used in OBAMA-NEXT Information Products and in general for marine ecology. However, different data might have specific particularities to be considered when selecting the approaches to be applied (Rubens et al., 2023). Therefore, the main categories of data types that are processed in order to generate OBAMA-NEXT Information Products useful for biodiversity monitoring and analysis are described in this chapter. Their relevance with respect to AI and statistical applications is illustrated by drawing on factual examples of AI research applications.

3.1. Genetic data

Molecular methods are quickly being transformed into routine tools for monitoring marine biodiversity and environmental status. Applications include specific assays (mainly qPCR or dPCR), DNA barcoding (DNA sequencing of single specimens), environmental DNA (eDNA) metabarcoding (targeting a specific taxonomic marker) or metagenomics (targeting total eDNA) (Cordier et al., 2018a; 2020). Over the last two decades, the cost of DNA sequencing has dropped steadily and exponentially, which has led to a rapid adoption and resulted in a deluge of DNA sequence data. The use of molecular tools for biomonitoring is a powerful alternative since it is less time consuming compared to traditional approaches (e.g., visual identification of organisms based on morphology).

The sheer size and heterogeneity of these datasets generated may limit the usefulness of traditional statistical inference approaches. Further, due to the ability of molecular approaches to target functional genes, microbial organisms or cryptic species, knowledge based on traditional morphology-based approaches for species identification can be insufficient. Supervised ML approaches have instead been promoted as promising alternatives for taking full advantage of sequencing datasets (Cordier et al., 2018). Several studies have also demonstrated advantages of such approaches for the prediction of environmental status directly or via the development of *de novo* biotic indices, compared to the use of existing biotic indices based on knowledge generated using traditional data analysis approaches (Dully et al., 2021; Cordier et al., 2017, 2018b; Brantschen et al., 2021; Lanzén et al., 2021; Keck et al., 2023). A particular issue with eDNA metabarcoding that can be overcome by this approach is also that the information produced (depending on the marker gene and reference databases used, or in some cases on cryptic diversity) does not correspond directly to the morphology-based taxonomy and counts of individuals of organisms needed by existing assessment indices (Frühe et al., 2020; Dully et al., 2021, Keck et al., 2023; Li et al., 2023). However, it deserves to be mentioned that eDNA-based methods also have limitations compared to traditional methods (Willassen et al., 2022; Duarte et al., 2023), due to the mobility of eDNA in the environment and its longevity in certain vectors, such as anoxic and muddy sediments.

There are also many examples of ML-based approaches for the analysis of eDNA sequence data that are not specific to only biomonitoring. This includes “denoising” of raw sequence data and thus automatic curation of biodiversity metrics (Callahan et al. 2016), taxonomic (Gregor et al., 2016) or functional gene prediction (reviewed by

Libbrecht and Noble, 2015), and prediction of ecological traits from metagenomic “bins” (groups of assembled data, ideally corresponding to individual species; Weimann et al., 2016).

The 18 initial Information Products listed in Deliverable 1.1 of OBAMA-NEXT (Borja et al., 2023), contain three related to the use of genetic data, which could include AI applications: (i) eDNA species distribution maps, which is in the concept proposal phase; (ii) eDNA run-off bioindicators, in the concept proposal phase; and (iii) a position paper on eDNA use for stakeholders, also in the concept proposal phase.

3.2. Remote sensing based data

Since 2014, the application of AI in the field of Earth observation (EO) has increased significantly due to methodological advances in deep learning methods and the open science culture (Camps-Valls et al., 2021). Moreover, ocean remote sensing has entered the big data era with typical five-V (volume, variety, value, velocity and veracity) characteristics, which pose a challenge to accurately, efficiently and intelligently extract the useful information buried in such a large amount of data (Li et al., 2020). The application areas of AI in EO include a wide range of tasks and applications such as data fusion, image classification, object and pattern detection, spatial and temporal reconstruction (Hill et al., 2020; Janga et al., 2023). In the field of EO applications related to marine environmental monitoring, there are two application areas that seem to be benefiting more with AI developments:

- **The generation of Essential Variables (EVs)** maps and time series that overcome the most common limitations of EO data sources, such as spatial and temporal data gaps, estimation uncertainties due to limited spectral bands or resolutions, etc. (Miloslavich et al., 2018). These problems can be overcome by data integration (Sagi et al., 2020), data fusion approaches using deep learning algorithms (Wang et al., 2023), gap-filling algorithms (Stock et al., 2020, Sarafanov et al., 2020) or merged/hybrid algorithms (Park et al., 2020; Staehr et al., 2022; Flores Junior et al., 2022; Stramski et al., 2023; Joshi et al., 2023).
- **The identification of marine objects and/or patterns** in remotely sensed imagery such as: shoreline detection and evolution monitoring (Tsiakos and Chalkias, 2023), delineation of intertidal and shallow water habitats such as coral reefs, salt marshes, deltas, mangroves or seagrasses (Wilson et al., 2020; Lathrop et al., 2022), wildlife censuses (i.e. marine birds, seals or whales) (Wang et al., 2019, Höschle et al., 2021), vessel monitoring (Salerno et al., 2023, Soldi et al., 2023), oil spills (Huby et al., 2022; Vasconcelos et al., 2023), debris and litter (Kikaki et al., 2022; Jia et al., 2023), detection of fronts and mesoscale features (Duo et al., 2019; Krinitskiy et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2023), sea ice monitoring (Ali et al., 2023) and phytoplankton functional groups or phytoplankton blooms detection (Fernandes-Salvador et al., 2021).

The 18 information products listed in Deliverable 1.1 (Borja et al., 2023) contain four IPs based on remote sensing data, which requires AI application in biodiversity monitoring: (i) In-situ observation of phytoplankton blooms, during the operational proposal phase; (ii) Coastal vegetation mapping – upscaled from drones to satellites, in development of the concept proposal initiated; (iii) Cyanobacteria bloom, in concept proposal; and (iv) Phytoplankton functional type map, in concept proposal.

3.3. Image based data

New imaging devices improve the capacity for data acquisition, expanding spatio-temporal coverage of observations. Yet, the large data volume generated by those devices is associated with new challenges for exploring the information contained in the data. AI algorithms are accelerating the acquisition, processing and dissemination of biodiversity data (Bicknell et al., 2016; Christin et al., 2019). AI methods provide possibilities for improving the discrimination of automated techniques, allowing large amounts of raw data to be converted to functional/taxonomical data and for predicting spatial and temporal distributions of different Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs)/Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) (Pereira et al., 2013; Kissling et al., 2018). EBVs are a small set of variables which collectively capture biodiversity change at multiple levels of biological organization and spatial scales that are of scientific and management interest (Schmeller et al., 2017; Jetz et al., 2019; Valdez et al., 2023).

AI showed early potential to automatically recognise phytoplankton and zooplankton from images (Zarauz et al., 2009; Irigoien et al., 2009) and promising results have been achieved in feature engineering methods (Sosik and Olson, 2007), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) (Luo, 2018; Kraft et al., 2022) and human-in-the-loop approaches (Schröder et al., 2020). The trade-off between taxa detail and performance is a common dilemma with this data (Fernandes et al., 2009). Furthermore, data harmonization among different devices can be also challenging due to variability in image characteristics (Grandremy et al., 2023). Imaging combined with AI has also been used for nekton and benthos species identification using video and images (Rubens et al., 2023). AI object detectors and segmentation localise species within images and video frames, and enable enumeration for abundance, biomass and coverage estimates (Galloway et al., 2022). These estimates can be further used with environmental measures to quantify and map ecosystem services (Schenone et al., 2021).

Image analysis and ML have been used with fishing vessel sonar (Uranga et al., 2017). Underwater cameras attached to fishing gears are used more often as a non-invasive method to assess populations of both pelagic (Rosen and Holst, 2013) and demersal (DeCelles et al., 2017) species. In demersal trawl fisheries, lack of light and poor visibility caused by suspended sediments (Krag et al., 2009; DeCelles et al., 2017), make the use of optical tools difficult. Electronic monitoring (EM) is an evolving tool utilized by managers and fisheries scientists to remotely monitor the catches and bycatch on-board commercial vessels (Lekunberri et al., 2022). The working environment aboard a fishing vessel provides unique challenges that can affect classification accuracy including difficult camera mounting locations, highly variable illumination, or fouling of the camera lens by dirt (Tseng and Kuo, 2020; Lekunberri et al., 2022).

Underwater imagery is particularly challenging with variable lighting and visually complex backgrounds which can be addressed by combining temporal information, in video, using optical flow, and Gaussian mixture models with CNNs in an ensemble can improve detection rates in visually complex scenarios (Jalal et al., 2020). Sequences of images can also be leveraged by computer vision (an AI subfield) 3D reconstructions algorithms, such as Structure-from-Motion (SfM) (Snavely et al., 2006), to extract high-resolution 3D geometric models. Morphological characteristics

of roughness and shape can be extracted from the 3D models (Friedman et al., 2012) and used as measures of habitat complexity in assessments of ecological biodiversity and abundance (Ferrari et al., 2018). These approaches have been popular in benthic community studies, in particular corals, and pair well with ROV and AUV platforms, which use cameras for navigation (Ferrari et al., 2016).

The 18 initial Information Products listed in Deliverable 1.1 (Borja et al., 2023), contain nine products related to image-based data, which could include AI application: (i) Seagrass mapping – distributions and ecological status, in development or semi-operational proposal phase; (ii) Suitability maps for seagrass restoration/repopulation, in concept phase; (iii) Fish distribution model/map, in concept phase; (iv) Population estimates of seabirds based on drone images and object recognition, in development or semi-operational proposal phase; (v) Population estimates of sea mammals based on drone images and object recognition, in development or semi-operational proposal phase; (vi) Data- and criteria-based identification of HD habitat types, in development of the concept proposal initiated; (vii) Underwater biodiversity hotspot map, in operational proposal phase; (viii) A map for allocating human activities at sea (e.g. offshore wind power), in development or semi-operational proposal phase; and (ix) Spatial distribution models for threatened species, in operational proposal phase.

3.4. Hybrid data approaches

Field surveys and experimental studies are often conducted in isolation, with their potential synergistic value largely overlooked. The incorporation of experimentally derived knowledge allows precise cause-and-effect relationships to be established, providing a clearer insight into potential shifts in ecosystem structure and function under future climatic conditions beyond projections based solely on statistical (non-causal) species distribution models (SDMs) and represents a major advance in the field of ecological modelling and forecasting (Queiros et al., 2015; Urban et al., 2016; Fernandes et al., 2017; Kotta et al., 2019). Furthermore, the integration of ML techniques with statistical modelling, remote sensing, and conventional spatial modelling variables such as coastal geomorphology and meteorological data has successfully identified, formulated and validated the functionality of abiotic environmental predictors on the distribution of species (Kotta et al., 2013; Vahtmäe et al., 2022).

For example, Kotta et al. (2013) showed that most benthic seaweed and invertebrate modelled species exhibit unique responses to their environmental conditions, providing a compelling argument for modelling individual species rather than communities (Kotta et al., 2013). The study used Principal Component Analysis (PCA) on selected CASI bands (5 to 16) to reduce data redundancy and compress the airborne captured hyperspectral images. This analysis revealed that the first three principal components closely resembled the structure of the original hyperspectral bands, effectively reducing data redundancy. The first principal component alone accounted for over 96% of the variance and was highly correlated with all CASI bands. Then, benthic macrophyte and invertebrate species cover was predicted with environmental variables (depth, hard bottom cover and waves exposure) and the PCA variables.

Another example is presented in Vahtmäe et al. (2022) where a hybrid model was developed which integrates in situ experimental data on photosynthetic production of algal communities, abiotic environmental variables such as light intensity and water temperature, and bottom reflectance spectra. This model was designed to assess the canopy-scale primary productivity of the Baltic Sea benthic vegetation. In their approach, the reflectance of algal communities was measured both in air and underwater. In a first step, the *in-situ* reflectance spectra of each algal community class were used to calculate different spectral indices, which were then correlated with chlorophyll a+b content. Indices using combinations of red and blue bands, such as 650/450 and 650/480 nm, were most effective in explaining chlorophyll variability in data sets measured both in air and underwater. The most efficient indices were then used in Boosted Regression Trees (BRT) models, along with meteorological data, to accurately predict photosynthesis in different algal community classes.

Changes in biodiversity and rapid shifts in species composition emphasize the critical need to monitor the functional diversity of communities. Although the availability of ecological monitoring data is increasing, much less progress has been made in automatically quantifying the physiological and ecological species traits needed to assess functional diversity. Ryabov et al. (2022) proposed using diffusion maps, a deterministic and virtually parameter-free manifold learning method, to estimate functional diversity and infer species functional traits directly from species abundance monitoring data. This method can be easily standardized and applied to a variety of ecological systems. Applying this approach to existing data provides a powerful tool to further our understanding of the influence of environmental factors on functional biodiversity. In community modelling and assessment joint species distribution models (jSDM; Ovaskainen et al., 2017; Vanhatalo et al., 2020) have shown significant improvements in predicting species community composition compared to standard statistical approaches where each species is modelled and predicted separately (Norberg et al., 2019; Fragkopoulou et al., 2022). However, jSDMs have not yet been extended for handling all available modern data sources nor tested in large-scale management applications. Moreover, examples of jSDM applications in modelling and predicting marine communities are rarer than in similar examples in the terrestrial setting (Vanhatalo et al., 2020; Weigel et al., 2021, 2023). JSDMs appear particularly promising for analysing and predicting species communities and handling sparse and relatively small datasets. In OBAMA-NEXT, jSDMs will be developed within Task 4.3 with the aim of modelling of multiple species and taxonomic groups simultaneously through joint species distribution models.

4. Sharing digital resources under FAIR, CARE and TRUST principles

Ensuring that digital resources are useful and manageable requires us to make them accessible, interoperable and reusable for both humans and computers (Huber, 2021). The **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles** were created with the aim of being a guide for improving data accessibility and reuse (Wilkinson, 2016). Data and code uploaded to aggregators or repositories ensure data availability for the final users (e.g. Zenodo or Github). However, FAIR principles aim to ensure an extensive and continuous reusability of rigorously evaluated data (Wilkinson et al., 2016), not only make them publicly available. These guidelines were defined to give support to the Open Science movement (Mons et al., 2017). Our recommendation is to follow the FAIR data principles using the recommendations provided in the OceanObs19 white paper (Tanhua et al., 2019). We also recommend using the Zenodo repository since it generates Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for final delivery. It also allows for updates and direct connection to the European Commission funding through its OpenAIRE feature, or in the use of Github resources for codes, also during development¹². Each letter of FAIR refers to a group of principles, each of them with sub-principles that must be accomplished, totalizing 15 principles that describe how the data must be to follow the FAIR principles (Jacobsen et al., 2020):

- **Findable:** Digital resources must be easy to find with appropriate metadata to identify relevant datasets and services by:
 - (i) must have a unique and persistent identifier;
 - (ii) have well-described metadata to facilitate search and filtering;
 - (iii) the metadata must contain the identifier of the data it describes;
 - (iv) registered or indexed in a searchable repository.
- **Accessibility:** Protocols for retrieving digital assets should be explicit with well-defined mechanisms for obtaining authorization to access protected data by:
 - (i) identifiers using a standardized communication protocol;
 - (ii) the protocol must be open, free and universally applicable;
 - (iii) the protocol allows for authentication and authorization if necessary;
 - (iv) the metadata must be accessible even if data are not available.
- **Interoperability:** Multiple digital resources should be able to merge information and be able to detect the conformity of the data by:
 - (i) use formal, accessible, common, and widely applicable language;
 - (ii) use vocabulary under FAIR principles (e.g. "Web Ontology Language");
 - (iii) metadata must include references to other data and metadata.
- **Reusability:** If the digital resources are sufficiently well described, the authorizing officer should know what task to use them for, whether they can be reused and under what conditions and to whom the use can be credited by:
 - (i) described in detail with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes;
 - (ii) published with a clear and accessible licence;
 - (iii) associated with detailed provenance;
 - (iv) comply with relevant industry standards.

¹ <https://the-turing-way.netlify.app/reproducible-research/rdm>

² <https://drivendata.github.io/cookiecutter-data-science/#data-is-immutable>

The **TRUST principles** (Lin, 2020) aim to go further by creating trusted digital repositories based on the trustworthiness. TRUST (Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability, and Technology) comprises the following principles:

- **Transparency** discusses making a repository as appropriate as possible by ensuring that the mission and scope of the repository are clearly stated. In addition, they should be transparent in the conditions for use of both the repository and data; minimum period of digital data preservation; and, any relevant additional features or services, for example, the ability to manage sensitive data responsibly.
- **Responsibility** stresses that repositories must take responsibility for managing and serving the community. Repository users must trust that depositors provide metadata and comply with community standards: metadata must conform to standards and standards preservation, technical validation, documentation, quality control, authenticity protection and long-term persistence; and manage the intellectual property rights of producers, the protection of sensitive information resources, and the security of the system and its contents.
- **User focus:** The use and reuse are an important part of the scientific process. Therefore, TRUSTworthy repositories should make it easier to find, explore and understand the digital resources. Repositories should encourage the provision of as much information as possible at the time of deposit to facilitate understanding and interoperability by following norms and standards in metadata, file formats, vocabularies, ontologies and other semantics. TRUSTworthy repository should: Implement data metrics and make them available to the users; provide community catalogues to facilitate data discovery; and monitoring and identifying evolving community expectations and meeting changing needs.
- **Sustainability:** To ensure uninterrupted access to a repository, it is important that the repository is sustainable. To this end, it must comply with the following criteria: plan well for risk mitigation, business continuity, disaster recovery and succession; secure funding to enable continued use and to maintain desirable data properties; and provide the necessary governance for long-term data preservation so that the data can remain accessible. Repositories are maintained through technology (software, hardware, and technical services).
- **Technology:** A repository should have the following technological capabilities: implement relevant standards, tools and technologies for data management and preservation; and plans and mechanisms in place to prevent, detect and respond to cyber and physical security threats.

To summarize the above principles, FAIR focuses more on data that are easy to identify and find, well-described, interoperable with other data and able to have more than one use. The CARE data principles seek to ensure that the data respects the rights of data provider as proposed in an application to indigenous data complementary to FAIR principles (Carroll et al., 2020). This principle provides a more social vision of the data highlighting the need of collective benefit and reciprocity not only the open access. TRUST focuses on making the data repositories trustworthy. For this, among other things, they must be clear about the conditions of use, data and metadata must comply with norms and standards and repositories must be constantly updated. The future of the repository must be guaranteed to ensure access to the data.

Wide differences in interpreting FAIR principles lead to misapplications, which minimize their interoperability and reusability. Partly because of this, representatives of the digital repository community developed the TRUST principles with the aim of demonstrating the reliability of repositories (Lin, 2020; Kinkade, 2021). A dataset may adhere to the FAIR principles but be suspect in terms of its quality or integrity status to allow reuse in research (Kinkade, 2021). The goal of FAIR and TRUST is to enable computers to identify and handle the data of interest and to be able to perform data analysis on that data. In this way, we can minimize time and cost and be more sustainable by using a dataset for different uses. From the planning stages of a research project, researchers should consider the types of data to be produced and inform themselves of the vocabularies available in the community, file formats, unit conventions and specific existing repositories (Kinkade, 2021).

In terms of accessibility and trust, tools or practices aimed at data interoperability are now available (Argo Programme, Environmental Research Division Data Access Programme (ERDDAP), Ocean Data View (ODV), Thematic Real-time Environmental Distributed Data Services (THREDDS), etc.). However, this underlines the need for data management planning and the adoption of FAIR principles (Tanhua, 2019). Many of today's data repositories follow FAIR principles, although the vast majority do not meet all the requirements in terms of data handling, formatting, and compliance (Schmidt, 2020). Marine imagery data is a problem because it is difficult to homogenize and create norms and standards for metadata (Schoening (2022)). According to Schoening (2022), the Planetary Data System (PDS4) standard is the best fit for these data, although it is not used because it does not cover all the requirements of marine science. The authors propose the image FAIR Digital Objects (iFDOs) standard for homogenization and compliance with FAIR principles.

In short, marine and oceanographic data have already started the process of meeting the principles of being accessible, interoperable, and trustworthy, although there is still a long way to go. There are also institutionally led repositories containing marine and oceanographic data that are within the World Data System (WDS) and/or CoreTrustSeal, which ensures that the data meet a minimum of the above-mentioned principles. In addition, the WDS has developed a prototype data portal with the aim of bringing together data from WDS members' catalogues, which was hosted by Pangaea. Registries such as FAIRsharing and Re3data, which have 743 identified geoscience repositories, can help locate suitable repositories to share their data. However, selecting the correct repository is not always easy (Enabling the FAIR Data Community et al., 2018). Kinkade et al. (2021) stress the importance of creating specialised domain repositories, in this way, repositories bring expertise to the process of data management, because they can bring together scientific knowledge and information management. Therefore, TRUST principles are also of vital importance.

For the AI algorithms, the concepts of explainability and transparency were included in most guidelines on Responsible AI (Fjeld et al., 2020) as well as legislation (e.g., the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Europe and the European Commission's draft Artificial Intelligence Act for high-risk AI applications on the European Market (European Commission, 2021). Also, in the field of geosciences, there is a clear call to move away from assessing merely the performance of AI algorithms and move forward towards the assessment of their quality (Craglia, 2018).

5. Trust building: statistical validation and ground truth testing

This section summarizes good practices in validating AI pipelines of methods from preprocessing to the final model and/or system. The need for honest validation considering all the process and not only the final model is highlighted. The approaches for a robust validation and comparison across models are also summarized. Walsh et al. (2023), in collaboration with a broad participation of the European bioinformatics community through the ELIXIR Machine Learning Focus Group, recently developed a set of general, improvable recommendations on data, optimization, modelling and evaluation (DOME; Walsh et al. 2023) when using ML in biological sciences. The most central recommendation of DOME is to include a brief “ML summary table” in all scientific publications based on ML and AI. However, it does not introduce the specific methodologies already extensively tested and discussed in computer science literature. In this chapter, this additional step of discussing specific methods and technique is done.

5.1. Preprocessing and modelling pipelines: design and validation

The process of developing AI-based systems consists of several steps, from data collection to learning a final model and the interpretation of results. The first step, the data collection, often implies other areas of expertise. The whole process does not just consist of learning a model from the collected data. In most cases, real-domain collected datasets are often not directly suitable for model induction, they contain noise and missing feature values, and therefore a significant pre-processing effort is required (Zhang et al., 2003). In particular, in certain domains such as those that manage annual climatic and environmental variables, data are sparse and difficult to manage. In these domains, appropriate data pre-processing can dramatically condition the final model and its performance (Fernandes et al., 2010; Uusitalo et al., 2007). Despite approaches dealing with robust predictors and validation under limited datasets, the performance of ML models can be improved by artificially increasing the amount of data (data augmentation). The specific augmentation techniques depend on the data type. For images, augmentation includes rotation, shifting, introducing noise and other perturbations (Ghosh et al., 2020). For time series, augmentation strategies include noise introduction, feature shuffling, time scale changes (Wen et al., 2021). In linguistic models, augmentation relies on synonym substitution, random word insertion and deletion. In the presence of rare (under-represented) classes, it also often involves the generation of synthetic examples (Chawla et al., 2002). Finally, there is a need to estimate the goodness of the whole model building a process or pipeline (pre-processing and model) in order to assess the usefulness, power and reliability of all the chain instead of only the final model itself (Reunanen et al., 2003; Statnikov et al., 2005; Fernandes et al., 2010, 2015). When the method uses the value of the target variable, known as supervised methods, there is high likelihood of overfitting when using non-parametric approaches (Dougherty et al., 1995; Kotsiantis et al., 2006).

Model design and validation for novel deep neural network architectures can be done in a piecewise manner. Systematically and iteratively removing network layers (layer ablation) and modules (module ablation) prior to training and evaluation can help to determine the contribution of each network component to the overall model

performance. This can aid in the construction of the final network by removing unnecessary modules/layers and can also aid in the final interpretability of the network by linking network design decisions to model behaviour (Girshick et al., 2014).

The choice of appropriate ML models depends on the specific research objectives (Tredennick et al., 2021). Different research goals place different and sometimes conflicting demands on the models. This discrepancy is most evident when comparing models for hypothesis testing and for prediction or image recognition. Hypothesis testing focuses on understanding the underlying dependencies of the model, such as how the target variable responds to changes in input parameters and whether this response is significant. In such scenarios, the preferred model should be simplified and suitable for rigorous statistical evaluation. Conversely, in predictive tasks, predictive accuracy comes first, and the subtleties of the relationship between response and input parameters may be less critical or too intricate for detailed study. In these cases, models with great flexibility and many adjustable internal parameters, such as random forests or neural networks, are often good options when data are plenty and the predictive task is interpolative in nature that is, predictions are made within spatial areas and environmental covariate values from where we have training data. However, when predicting in extrapolative manner, that is predicting far from the training data in terms of either spatial distance or covariate similarity, machine learning methods often fail compared to more rigid parametric statistical models (Hartman et al., 2017; Norberg et al., 2019).

5.2. Robust statistical validation

The model performance must be assessed to establish the expected error. This is accomplished by dividing the user-labelled dataset into two parts: training and evaluation. Depending upon the selected evaluation technique, this demarcation can be undertaken one or several times, with different data sampling techniques (Fernandes et al., 2011). One of the simplest approaches consists of leaving part of the data for learning the model, with the remainder used for validation, *i.e.* 'hold-out' (Larson, 1931). However, the estimated performance can be sensitive to changes in data partition, especially in small datasets (Rodríguez et al., 2009). It can be addressed by data partition into *k*-folds: each fold is left out of the model learning process and used as a test set, repeatedly, *k* times. The estimated performance is the average of *k* learned models, *i.e.* 'cross-validation' (Lachenbruch and Mickey, 1968). The extreme data partition is to split the data into as many folds as possible, leaving one data instance per fold, *i.e.* 'leaving one out cross-validation' (LOOCV; Mosteller and Tukey, 1968). This method has the advantage of leaving a large part of the data for learning but is computationally expensive. Moreover, splitting the data into training and test sets should account for the predictive task in hand so that, for example, models extrapolative and interpolative predictive performance should be tested with different types of cross-validation strategies (Vanhatalo et al., 2012; Roberts et al., 2017; Vanhatalo et al., 2020; Kettunen et al., 2023). Variance related to cross-validation summaries can be decreased using re-sampling, with replacement, where the data is re-sampled and the probability of data duplication is considered in the performance estimation, *i.e.* 'bootstrapping' (Efron, 1979). However, this approach is computationally expensive. Such validation processes may be repeated using

different partitions of the data, with the results being averaged to ensure replicability, e.g. 10-times-repeated 5-fold cross-validation (Bouckaert and Frank, 2004) and perform algorithm comparison with a statistical test, e.g. corrected paired t-test (Nadeau and Bengio, 2003).

All approaches have advantages and disadvantages; as such, they must be selected depending upon the data characteristics and validation objectives. However, most recruitment prediction works' validation limits to look for model fitness using the same data for learning and testing, or they validate using 'hold-out' methods that have limited reliability (Dreyfus-León and Chen, 2007; Dreyfus-León and Schweigert, 2008; Schirripa and Colbert, 2006).

In general, stratified ten-fold cross-validation or its repeated version n-times repeated k-fold cross-validation stand out as methods that show a good trade-off between robust error estimation and computational time when the interest is assessing models' performances (Bouckaert and Frank, 2004; Rodriguez et al., 2010). The stratification implies that the folds contain approximately the same proportions of classes as the original dataset. Finally, the n-repeated k-fold cross-validation consists in repeating n times the cross-validation with different data randomizations. The repeated cross-validation allows avoiding results dependant on data partition, performing more robust results comparisons (statistical tests) as well as reporting more stable and robust performances by means of averaging the repeats. Often pipelines of pre-processing and modelling methods are applied to data. The entire pipeline must be included in the validation scheme to avoid model over-fitting and provide an honest validation (Reunanen et al., 2003; Statnikov et al., 2005; Fernandes et al., 2010, 2015). This means that the data partition, in folds, is performed before the application of the first step of the pipeline. Therefore, not only the classification model, but also all the pipeline is validated.

Finally, the presented methods are resampling methods that are used for error evaluation. However, these methods can be used also for parameter estimation as used in Schirripa and Colbert (2006) or for more stable feature selection as indicated in Francis et al. (2006) and Fernandes et al. (2010).

5.3. Models' comparison with statistical tests

The choice of which specific learning algorithm should be used often needs to be done assessing the performance of multiple algorithms. A common method is to perform statistical comparisons of the performance measures of trained classifiers on specific datasets (Kotsiantis et al., 2007). If there are sufficient data, several training sets can be sampled, both learning algorithms can be applied to each of them, and the difference in accuracy for each pair of classifiers on a large test set can be estimated. In frequentist approaches, the next step is to perform a statistical test (e.g., paired t-test) to check the null hypothesis that the mean difference between the classifiers is zero. This test can produce two types of errors. Type I error is the probability that the test rejects the null hypothesis incorrectly (i.e. it finds a significant difference although there is none). Type II error is the probability that the null hypothesis is not rejected when there actually is a difference. The test's Type I error will be close to the chosen significance level. Different training sets are obtained by subsampling, and the

instances not sampled for training are used for testing. Unfortunately, this violates the independence assumption necessary for proper significance testing. The consequence of this is that Type I errors exceed the significance level. Several heuristic versions of the t-test have been developed to alleviate this problem (Dietterich, 1998; Nadeau and Bengio, 2003). Ideally, it would be desirable for the outcome of the test to be independent of a single partitioning resulting from the randomization process because this would make it much easier to replicate experimental results published in the literature. However, in practice there is always certain sensitivity to the partitioning used. To measure replicability, we need to repeat the same test several times on the same data with different random partitions and count how often the outcome is the same (Bouckaert et al., 2003, 2004). Therefore, we recommend the use of the corrected paired t-test (Nadeau and Bengio, 2003) using 10-times 5-fold cross-validation. This paired t-test is conservative and can result in higher p-values than other less strict tests (e.g., paired t-test). In Bayesian approach, the choice between the best models is based on formal decision theoretic considerations applied, for example, through cross validation (Vehtari and Ojanen, 2014).

Figure 2. Distribution of the posterior probabilities for Bcscx, Greedy and GreedyBcscx crossovers obtained from the Bayesian ranking analysis in Granado et al. (2024).

The comparison of multiple methodologies over multiple datasets can be performed by means of the revised Friedman plus Shaffer's static post-hoc test, proposed by (Garcia and Herrera, 2008) for comparison of multiple methods over multiple datasets. These statistical test results can be represented by means of critical difference diagrams (Demšar et al., 2006; Fernandes et al., 2013; Singh et al., 2015), which show the average ranks of the performance of each method across all the domains in a numbered line. If there is not a statistically significant difference between two methods, they are connected in the diagram by a straight line. Another example is the Bayesian analysis based on the probabilistic Plackett-Luce (PL) model. In a nutshell, the approach works by running different number of instances of the problem, then rank them according to the value of the objective function and, finally use the PL model to analyse the set of rankings. The advantages of this method are that it allows us to obtain the probability of an algorithm being the best along with its uncertainty when comparing multiple algorithms at the same time. This Bayesian approach was suggested in (Calvo et al., 2018) and it is implemented in the scmamp R package (Calvo and Santafé, 2016). In an example comparing several genetic operators from

Granado et al. (2024), it can be visually observed that one of the operators outperforms the other (Fig. 2).

Achieving high prediction accuracy does not guarantee reliable generalization or absence of false inferences. For example, CNNs may favour textures, such as animal hair patterns, for classification, and become unstable with respect to weak image perturbation. Similarly, random forest models may learn to utilize irrelevant data tags for classification. In critical areas such as environmental policy and public health, making informed decisions is of paramount importance (Vayena et al., 2018). To understand the mechanics of a predictive model, it is crucial to understand how the model's prediction depends on the input variables and interpret the results (Ribeiro et al., 2016c; Molnar, 2018). While simple models such as Ridge or LASSO regression enable direct interpretation, more complex models such as neural networks, random forests, etc., require additional analysis (Walsh et al., 2023).

Model interpretation can be performed at three levels (Lucas, 2020). At the global level, we evaluate the overall ability of the model to make correct predictions and identify outliers. In doing so, it is useful to generate unfavourable examples leading to credible but false predictions (Szegedy et al., 2020). At the second level, we assess the importance of individual variables and their partial effects on model response. The variable importance can be assessed as absolute values of coefficients of a linear regression, and, for more complex models, as the dependence of the prediction error on data permutation in this variable or variable ablation. Partial dependencies, in turn, reveal the major dependences of the model response on one variable, averaged over different values of other variables. The third level of interpretation involves examining local model behaviour at some key points, e.g. slopes of response dependence on the most important variables. These approaches identify the model critical features and help to obtain more reliable and interpretable prognoses.

5.4. Ground truth validation

Despite efforts to validate models, biased training data and over confidence on expert knowledge is likely one of the main issues when statistically tested AI models underperform in real environment final operationalization (Culverhouse et al., 2003; Sun et al., 2020). Therefore, there is the need for additional testing with another source of "truth", i.e. another type of data or knowledge that can challenge our results beyond train/test data partition. For example, in Taconet et al. (2019) classification of vessels activity was compared with a database of catches to identify discrepancies. While none of both datasets could be considered to be the truth, the inconsistencies allowed to identify some weaknesses of the AI work when compared with another truth based on other type of data not used for the AI system development, even if this ground truth has its own biases. Another example is the comparison of fish species classification and size in Lekunberri et al. (2021). In this example, the AI-based estimations, based on image analysis and deep learning on the vessels, were compared with the estimations based on port samplings. While both approaches have their own limitations and biases, the comparison highlighted that AI was underestimating size and biased towards specific species depending on the fishing method. Another example is demonstrated by Traganos et al. (2022), who used the results from localized mapping studies from different parts of the Mediterranean to validate a

Mediterranean-wide seagrass mapping process based on Sentinel-2 satellite imagery. In addition, the validation studies were done in higher resolution and utilized traditional methods in data collection.

In cases, where models are developed with lower spatial resolution data to target resolution-costs trade-offs, models created using higher spatial resolution data could function as ground truthing. A good example of this is present in Pucino et al. (2022), where the AI shoreline estimation models using Sentinel 2 images were validated against a unique ground truth derived from a combination of digital surface models from high-resolution UAV imagery and water level estimation using buoy data and tidal modelling. The UAV imagery was collected within two hours of the satellite overpass in order to provide high temporal alignment, which offered a significantly better resolution on shoreline variance. The finer resolution ground truth allowed deeper beach-scale spatial variability analysis of the coarser satellite models.

ML models can also be validated using synthetic data simulated based on computer models that contain all the necessary ground truth information for direct testing. For example, Ryabov et al. (2022) proposed using diffusion maps to estimate functional biodiversity based solely on species abundance data. Species distribution models testing can also benefit from comparison with standardized survey data (Fernandes et al., 2020a; 2020b).

6. Policy needs

In Europe, there are several legislation and policy instruments which bring the use of AI to the forefront, or which support the use of this technology in the near future to monitor and assess the status of marine ecosystems. In this section, we give an overview of the main legislature and policy instruments, with a special focus on those highlighted by the Practitioners Advisory Board of the OBAMA-NEXT project, in order of their priorities (see also Deliverable 6.1; Walton et al., 2023). These are the Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA), Nature Restoration Law (NRL), Birds and Habitats Directives (BHD), Water Framework Directive (WFD), Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), Regional Seas Conventions (RSC), Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030, the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and the European Green Deal. Across several of these instruments, there is potential relevance for AI in terms of monitoring and reporting obligations. To meet these obligations, Member States need information on the present state of species, habitats, and ecosystems, both their physical and chemical components, and changes to their composition or quality over a given time frame. This implies large data needs and heterogenous sources of data (Walton et al., 2023). These data needs, in turn, are not always easily comparable across countries, at either a European (or other regional) level or at an international level, hampering the understanding of progress towards high level commitments or contracting party compliance (for instance, with reference to the UN Convention on Biological Diversity and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework).

6.1. The Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA)

The main objective of the AIA is to ensure that the use of AI is safe and respects existing laws on fundamental rights and European Union values, and contributes towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goals under the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (Vinuesa et al., 2020; Palomares et al., 2021). AI could have a positive impact on 134 targets (79%) across all SDGs (Vinuesa et al., 2020). The advantages provided by AI may also have a positive impact on 42 targets (70%) from several SDGs within the Economy group (Vinuesa et al., 2020). The AI-related review undertaken by Fernandes-Salvador et al., 2022 found several facts that are relevant for biodiversity: 1) there is no explicit reference to AI systems in the most relevant EU fisheries legislation, but there are references to digitalisation that could include AI systems; 2) the most relevant fisheries legislation is drafted in a way that enables the use of AI systems; 3) the broad-ranging nature of the AIA proposal makes its application to the fisheries sector straightforward; 4) there are some concerns that the GDPR would require adaptation to the new realities brought by AI technologies; 5) Machine Learning approaches have been extensively used to automate biological sample processing; 6) Machine Learning has been applied after image analysis and on acoustic data to count and measure organisms; 7) research on catch classification by species and sizes using AI has increased; 8) Machine Learning is being applied to automatically classify or determine fishers' behaviour; 9) knowledge-based and expert systems have been applied to early warning systems and marine spatial planning; 10) traditional rule-based expert systems have been mainly applied in data-limited situations; 11) statistical approaches, Bayesian estimation, search and optimization

methods are not traditionally considered AI, but can be integrated into AI systems; 12) fishing vessels could improve energy efficiency and reduce their CO₂ footprint by using AI systems. Main obstacles identified (Fernandes-Salvador et al., 2022) to the use of AI in fisheries and marine research are: 1) industry trust and reluctance; 2) initial costs and lack of expertise; and 3) legal and bureaucratic uncertainty.

6.2. Nature Restoration Law (NRL)

The European Commission's proposal for a NRL is the first comprehensive regional law of its kind. It is a key element of the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, which calls for binding targets to restore degraded ecosystems. The proposal combines an overarching restoration objective for the long-term recovery of nature in the EU's land and sea areas with binding restoration targets for specific habitats and species. These commitments aim to restore at least 20% of the EU's land and sea areas by 2030, and ultimately all ecosystems in need of restoration by 2050. The proposal contains the following specific target relevant for marine ecosystems: restoring marine habitats such as seagrass beds or sediment bottoms that deliver significant benefits, including for climate change mitigation, and restoring the habitats of iconic marine species such as dolphins and porpoises, sharks and seabirds (European Commission, 2022). The determination of measures shall be based on the best available knowledge and the latest scientific evidence of the condition of the habitats, measured by the structure and functions which are necessary for their long-term maintenance, including their typical species. Article 5 of the NRL includes several obligations for Member States (e.g. to ensure that the areas that are subject to restoration measures show a continuous improvement in the condition of the habitat types until good condition is reached, and of the quality of the habitats of the species until the sufficient quality of those habitats is reached) might require application of several approaches and methods outlined in AIA. The European Commission, in its proposal for the law, expressly noted the relevance of new technologies, including AI, to "increase the speed, effectiveness and coherence of multiple monitoring and reporting processes" (2022/0195 (COD) at 10 and see proposed Art 17 in the same document on the detailed monitoring proposals and reference to AI in supporting these).³

6.3. The EU Habitats and Birds Directives (HBD)

The implementation of the European Union's Directives on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora (92/43/EEC) (European Commission, 1992) and on the conservation of wild birds (79/409/EEC) constitutes an important step towards the harmonization of nature conservation in the European Union. The HBD aims to protect species, including birds, mammals, reptiles, amphibians, fish and invertebrates, and characteristic habitat types. The overall objective is to ensure that these species and habitat types are maintained, or restored, to a favourable conservation status within the EU. In addition to halting the further decline or disappearance of these species and habitats, the Directive aims to allow them to recover and thrive over the long-term. The HBD requires Member States to monitor the conservation status of the habitats and species listed in the Directive (Art. 11) and

³ This position is retained in the most recent version of the proposal, adopting the European Council's 'General Approach'; see [st10867-en23.pdf \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/st10867-en23.pdf)

to report periodically (Art. 17). Every six years, Member States must report to the Commission on the conservation status of species and habitat types protected under the HD that are present on their territory. Several scientific parameters are used to assess their status (good, poor, bad) across their natural range within the EU. As such, conservation status of habitats and species is then assessed in a report every six years at the biogeographical level through a process which aggregates all the individual Member State reports per EU subregion. The HBD reporting requires performing consistent and systematic monitoring, data management and analysis. While the date of the Directive means that it does not include references to AI or similar, there is nevertheless good scope to implement various AI approaches and techniques in data collection and analysis (both on species and habitats) to assist with monitoring and reporting obligations- see AIA section above.

6.4. The EU Water Framework Directive (WFD)

The WFD was the first attempt to manage the complete water cycle, from rivers, through transitional waters, until coastal waters (European Commission, 2000). The EU Member States should achieve good ecological and chemical status in all water bodies, using their own methods to assess the status under an intercalibration process (European Commission, 2018). The Directive includes reduction and minimisation of pollution, aimed at achieving good status for EU waters by 2015 (later by 2021 and now by 2027), which require monitoring. This monitoring, regarding transitional and coastal waters, includes phytoplankton, macroalgae, seagrasses, macroinvertebrates and fish (these, only in transitional waters). The use of AI tools can be useful in relation to several of the broad obligations under the WFD including monitoring and assessing those biological elements, but also in the physico-chemical and chemical elements, as shown also in Section 6.5.

6.5. The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)

The MSFD represents a major contribution to the conservation, protection, and restoration of marine ecosystems (European Commission, 2008). The EU Member States should progressively work towards achieving good environmental status to ensure that the seas are clean, healthy, and productive, and to reduce the impact of human activities on marine ecosystems, using some guidelines in the application of criteria and methodological standards (European Commission, 2017). Pressures from human activities should be kept at levels compatible with good environmental status, and to keep commercially exploited fish stocks, as well as those of other marine animals, stable within safe biological limits, to ensure their long-term sustainability. It includes reduction and minimisation of pollution, aimed at achieving good environmental status for EU waters by 2026, which require monitoring. It should be underlined that the MSFD dates from 2008. Therefore, references to AI technology are logically absent. The preamble to the MSFD recognises, however, (recital 34) that marine strategies should be regularly updated because of the need for them to 'be flexible and adaptive and take account of scientific and technological developments'. The use of AI can be useful to several of the obligations under the MSFD including the preparation of the Marine Strategies referred to in Chapter II of the Directive, both in their assessment phase (Article 8), in the determination of good environmental status

(Article 9), and in the establishment and implementation of monitoring programmes (Article 11). They might also be appropriate instruments to reinforce the monitoring programmes referred to in Annex V, or the programmes of measures indicated in Annex VI. Monitoring requirements (Annex 5 (12)) include ‘evaluating the trends towards the achievement of the environmental targets [in Art 10]’.

AI combined with image analysis has demonstrated its capacity for large amount of sample processing as well as a large amount of indicators estimation (Fernandes et al., 2009; Irigoien et al., 2009; Uusitalo et al., 2016). Indicators seems to have a central role not only on MSFD monitoring, but also on the planning of solutions such as nature-based solutions (Garmendia et al., 2023; Murillas et al., 2023). Among the different criteria and indicators, proposed by the European Commission (2017), for the MSFD implementation, some of them are susceptible to be studied using AI, e.g:

- (Descriptor 1: biodiversity) the identification of some species of fish, marine mammals and seabirds, using massive images data (Pollicelli et al., 2020),
- (Descriptor 2: non-indigenous species) the identification of non-indigenous species (Bloomfield et al., 2021),
- (Descriptor 3: commercial fish) automatic measurements of fish size on-board (Lekunberri et al., 2022), or
- (Descriptor 5: eutrophication) identification of Harmful Algal Blooms using satellite or modelled data (Hill et al., 2020; Fernandes-Salvador et al., 2021).
- Descriptor 6: seafloor integrity – the automatic classification of side-sonar data (Breyer et al., 2023).

6.6. Regional Seas Conventions (RSC)

The Regional Seas Programmes support transboundary cooperation on marine policy, including for biodiversity and ecosystems, between neighbouring countries at the sea-basin level. RSCs have, in some cases, adopted the concept of “Good Environmental Status”, as seen in the MSFD and the contracting parties have assessment and reporting commitments, of varying degrees, related to this under RSCAPs. The action plans set out a range of indicators and objectives. There are four RSCs relevant to European marine policy, of which the European Commission is a contracting party to all but the Bucharest Convention:

- The Barcelona Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Region of the Mediterranean (1995) (UNEP-MAP)
- The Bucharest Convention on the Protection of the Black Sea Against Pollution (1992) (BSAP)
- Helsinki Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area (1992) (HELCOM)
- The Oslo and Paris (OSPAR) Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (1992)

In the case of HELCOM, the BSAP makes several references to the need to make use of best available scientific knowledge and technologies. The use of several AI tools is already in place to address the variety of BSAP objectives (either in monitoring, data analysis and assessment) and will likely be intensified in future. These include, amongst others, species identifications by image analysis, automation of monitoring

of the marine environment, identifying links between human activities, pressures and ecosystem state components, and commercial fish stock assessments (Fernandes et al., 2012; Uusitalo et al., 2016). More broadly, RSCAPs incorporate the principle of Best Available Technique or Best Available Technology (BAT).

6.7. The Common Fisheries Policy (CFP)

The CFP aims to ensure that fisheries and aquaculture activities are environmentally sustainable in the long term and are managed generating economic, social and employment benefits and contributing to the availability of foodstuffs (Article 2(1) of CFP Framework Regulation). CFP finds in the AI system an appropriate instrument for these purposes. The CFP Framework Regulation refers to data collection and processing in several paragraphs since it considers that ‘fisheries management based on the best available scientific advice requires harmonised, reliable, and accurate data sets’ (recital 46). Additionally, it indicates that ‘Member States should collect data on fleets and their fishing activities, in particular biological data on catches, including discards and survey information on fish stocks and on the potential environmental impact of fishing activities on the marine ecosystem. Member States should manage and make the collected data available to end-users and to other interested parties’ (recital 46). Furthermore, this Regulation stresses that ‘policy-oriented fisheries science should be reinforced by means of nationally adopted fisheries scientific data collection, research and innovation programmes’ (recital 49). It also underlines the importance of exchanging relevant information to ensure sustainable exploitation of fisheries resources and management thereof consistent with the objectives of CFP (recital 51). Additionally, the CFP Framework Regulation includes the wish of promoting ‘the use of modern and effective technologies [...] in the framework of the Union control, inspection, and enforcement’, stating that ‘Member States and the Commission should have the possibility of conducting pilot projects on new control technologies and data management systems’ (recital 60). It concludes by integrating private operators in data collection (recital 64). The reference in Recital 60 to new control technologies could be applicable to the use of AI system and the rest of recitals are applicable to the data needed to develop AI systems.

6.8. The EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030

The EU’s biodiversity strategy for 2030 is a “comprehensive, ambitious and long-term plan to protect nature and reverse the degradation of ecosystems”. The strategy aims to put Europe’s biodiversity on a path to recovery by 2030. The key commitments of the Biodiversity Strategy related to the marine realm (legally protect a minimum of 30% of the EU’s Sea area and integrate ecological corridors, as part of a true Trans-European Nature Network; and effectively manage all protected areas, defining clear conservation objectives and measures, and monitoring them appropriately) require coordinated pan-European approaches in monitoring and assessment of the progress. The Strategy makes a specific commitment to the use of technology and research which provides an underpinning rationale for the use of new technologies such as AI (3.4 Improving knowledge, education and skills). Investing in research, innovation and knowledge exchange will be key to gathering the best data and developing the best nature-based solutions. Research and innovation can test and develop how to

prioritise ‘green’ solutions and help the Commission to support investments in nature-based solutions. Amongst others, relevant AI approaches are related to application of already existing and development of new autonomous sensors / sampling platforms, species image analysis, spatial habitat mapping, connectivity modelling, data management, application of ML approaches in data analysis and performing cumulative effects assessments.

6.9. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, adopted in 2015 (A/Res/70/1), establishes a roadmap for “ending poverty, protecting the planet and tackling inequalities”⁴. The 2030 Agenda aims to drive significant changes, directly addressing the conservation and sustainable management of ecosystems. As part of this roadmap, the 2030 Agenda establishes Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) with 169 associated targets. Among the key targets of the SDGs is the need to strengthen resilience and adaptive capacity to climate-related disasters. This involves implementing strategies that not only mitigate the adverse effects of climate change but also prepares communities to withstand and recover from its impacts. The adoption of the SDGs on oceans and seas represents a unique opportunity to enhance marine governance and management globally. SDG14 is indeed a far-reaching goal designed to reverse biodiversity loss, conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas, and marine resources for sustainable development. This involves clear conservation objectives, ensuring robust monitoring mechanisms. New technologies coupled with AI can enable automated and remote monitoring of the sea. In its 2023 assessment of the SDGs, the UN noted digital transformation, including the use of AI, as a lever for the realisation of the SDGs⁵ including marine spatial planning (Coccoli et al., 2019).

6.10. The Green Deal

The European Green Deal (2019) sets out an overarching vision for economic growth which incorporates tackling climate change and other environmental challenges. The Green Deal is a whole-economy policy which sets out several commitments across multiple sectors. With reference to ‘mobilising industry for a clean and circular economy (2.1.3), the Green Deal recognises that digital technologies are a “critical enabler for attaining the sustainability goals of the Green deal in many different sectors.” The policy commits to exploring measures such as AI, 5G, cloud and edge computing and the internet of things can “accelerate and maximise the impact of policies to deal with climate change and protect the environment”.

⁴ United Nations, ‘The Sustainable Development Agenda’ at The Sustainable Development Agenda - United Nations Sustainable Development.

⁵ : Independent Group of Scientists appointed by the Secretary-General, Global Sustainable Development Report 2023: Times of crisis, times of change: Science for accelerating transformations to sustainable development, (United Nations, New York, 2023).

References

- Ali, S., Huang, Y., Wang, J. (2023). AI for sea ice forecasting. In *Artificial Intelligence in Earth Science* (pp. 41–58). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-91737-7.00012-8>
- Barroso, V. R., Xavier, F. C., & Ferreira, C. E. L. (2023). Applications of machine learning to identify and characterize the sounds produced by fish. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 80(7), 1854-1867.
- Bicknell, A. W., Godley, B. J., Sheehan, E. V., Votier, S. C., Witt, M. J. (2016). Camera technology for monitoring marine biodiversity and human impact. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 14(8), 424-432.
- Bloomfield, N. J., Wei, S., A. Woodham, B., Wilkinson, P., Robinson, A. P. (2021). Automating the assessment of biofouling in images using expert agreement as a gold standard. *Scientific reports*, 11(1), 2739.
- Borja, A., H. Ojaveer, R. Walton, M. Teli, H. Einberg, J. Carstensen, 2023. OBAMA-NEXT D1.1: Initial specification information product catalogue fulfilling societal/policy needs. 31 pp.
- Breyer, G., Bartholomä, A. Pesch, R. 2023. The Suitability of Machine-Learning Algorithms for the Automatic Acoustic Seafloor Classification of Hard Substrate Habitats in the German Bight. *Remote Sens* 15(16), 4113; <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15164113>
- Bouckaert, R.R., Frank, E., 2004. Evaluating the replicability of significance tests for comparing learning algorithms. In: *Proceedings of the 8th Pacific-Asian Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, Australia, pp. 3–12.
- Brantschen, J.; Blackman, R. C.; Walser, J.-C. Altermatt, F. (2021), 'Environmental DNA gives comparable results to morphology-based indices of macroinvertebrates in a large-scale ecological assessment', *PLOS ONE* 16(9), e0257510.
- Callahan, B. J.; McMurdie, P. J.; Rosen, M. J.; Han, A. W.; Johnson, A. J. Holmes, S. P. (2016), 'DADA2: High resolution sample inference from amplicon data', *Nature Methods*.
- Calvo, B., Santafé, G. (2016). scmamp: Statistical comparison of multiple algorithms in multiple problems. *R Journal*, 8(1), 248–256.
- Calvo, B., Ceberio, J., Lozano, J. A. (2018). Bayesian inference for algorithm ranking analysis. *GECCO 2018 Companion - Proceedings of the 2018 Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference Companion*, 324–325.
- Carroll, S. R., Garba, I., Figueroa-Rodríguez, O. L., Holbrook, J., Lovett, R., Materechera, S., ... & Hudson, M. (2020). The CARE principles for indigenous data governance. *Data Science Journal*, 19, 43-43.
- Chawla, N. V., Bowyer, K. W., Hall, L. O., Kegelmeyer, W. P. (2002). SMOTE: synthetic minority over-sampling technique. *Journal of artificial intelligence research*, 16, 321-357.
- Christin, S., Hervet, É., Lecomte, N. (2019). Applications for deep learning in ecology. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 10(10), 1632-1644.
- Coccoli, C., Galparsoro, I., Murillas, A., Pınarbaşı, K., & Fernandes, J. A. (2018). Conflict analysis and reallocation opportunities in the framework of marine spatial planning: a novel, spatially explicit Bayesian belief network approach for artisanal fishing and aquaculture. *Marine Policy*, 94, 119-131.
- Cordier, T., Esling, P., Lejzerowicz, F., Visco, J., Ouadahi, A., Martins, C., ... & Pawlowski, J. (2017). Predicting the ecological quality status of marine environments from eDNA metabarcoding data using supervised machine learning. *Environmental science & technology*, 51(16), 9118-9126.
- Cordier, T.; Alonso-Sáez, L.; Apothéloz-Perret-Gentil, L.; Aylagas, E.; Bohan, D. A.; Bouchez, A.; Chariton, A.; Creer, S.; Frühe, L.; Keck, F.; Keeley, N.; Laroche, O.; Leese, F.; Pochon, X.; Stoeck, T.; Pawlowski, J. Lanzén, A. (2020), 'Ecosystems monitoring powered by environmental genomics: a review of current strategies with an implementation roadmap', *Molecular Ecology* 30, 2937--2958.
- Cordier, T.; Lanzén, A.; Apothéloz-Perret-Gentil, L.; Stoeck, T. Pawlowski, J. (2018a), 'Embracing Environmental Genomics and Machine Learning for Routine Biomonitoring', *Trends in Microbiology* 27(5), 387--397.
- Cordier, T.; Forster, D.; Dufresne, Y.; Martins, C. I. M.; Stoeck, T. Pawlowski, J. (2018b), 'Supervised machine learning outperforms taxonomy-based environmental DNA metabarcoding applied to biomonitoring', *Molecular Ecology Resources* 18, 1381--1391.
- Craglia, M., (2018). *Artificial intelligence: a European perspective*. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/10.2760/936974>.
- Culverhouse, P. F., Williams, R., Reguera, B., Herry, V., González-Gil, S. (2003). Do experts make mistakes? A comparison of human and machine identification of dinoflagellates. *Marine ecology progress series*, 247, 17-25.
- DeCelles, G. R., Keiley, E. F., Lowery, T. M., Calabrese, N. M., Stokesbury, K. D. E. 2017. Development of a Video Trawl Survey System for New England Groundfish. *Transactions of the American Fisheries Society*, 146: 462–477.
- Demšar, J. (2006). Statistical comparisons of classifiers over multiple data sets. *The Journal of Machine learning research*, 7, 1-30.

- Dietterich, T. G. (1998). Approximate statistical tests for comparing supervised classification learning algorithms. *Neural computation*, 10(7), 1895-1923.
- Dougherty, J., Kohavi, R., Sahami, M., 1995. Supervised and unsupervised discretization of continuous features. In: A. Prieditis and S. Russell, (eds.), *Proceedings of International Conference on Machine Learning*. Morgan Kaufmann, San Francisco, CA, USA, pp. 194-202.
- Dreyfus-León, M., Chen, D.G., 2007. Recruitment prediction with genetic algorithms with application to the Pacific Herring fishery. *Ecological Modelling* 203 (1–2), 141–146.
- Dreyfus-León, M., Schweigert, J., 2008. Recruitment prediction for Pacific herring (*Clupea pallasii*) on the west coast of Vancouver Island, Canada. *Ecological Informatics* 3(2), 202–206.
- Duarte, S., P. E. Vieira, B. R. Leite, M. A. L. Teixeira, J. M. Neto, F. O. Costa, 2023. Macrozoobenthos monitoring in Portuguese transitional waters in the scope of the water framework directive using morphology and DNA metabarcoding. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 281: 108207.
- Duffy, J. E., Benedetti-Cecchi, L., Trinanes, J., Muller-Karger, F. E., Ambo-Rappe, R., Boström, C., ... & Yaakub, S. M. (2019). Toward a coordinated global observing system for seagrasses and marine macroalgae. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 6, 317.
- Dully, V.; Wilding, T. A.; Mühlhaus, T.; Stoeck, T. 2021. Identifying the minimum amplicon sequence depth to adequately predict classes in eDNA-based marine biomonitoring using supervised machine learning. *Computational and Structural Biotechnology Journal* 19, 2256-2268. doi: 10.1016/j.csbj.2021.04.005.
- Duo, Z., Wang, W., Wang, H. (2019). Oceanic Mesoscale Eddy Detection Method Based on Deep Learning. *Remote Sensing*, 11(16), 1921. MDPI AG. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs11161921>
- Efron, B., 1979. Bootstrap methods: another look at the jackknife. *Annals of Statistics*, 7 (1), 1–26.
- European Commission, 1992. Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora. *Official Journal of the European Union*, 206: 7–50.
- European Commission, 2000. Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for community action in the field of water policy. *Official Journal of the European Union*, L327: 1-72.
- European Commission, 2008. Directive 2008/56/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a framework for community action in the field of marine environmental policy (Marine Strategy Framework Directive). *Official Journal of the European Union*, L164: 19-40.
- European Commission, 2017. Commission Decision (EU) 2017/848 of 17 May 2017 laying down criteria and methodological standards on good environmental status of marine waters and specifications and standardised methods for monitoring and assessment, and repealing Decision 2010/477/EU *Official Journal of the European Communities*, L125: 43-74.
- European Commission, 2018. Commission Decision (EU) 2018/229 of 12 February 2018 establishing, pursuant to Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, the values of the Member State monitoring system classifications as a result of the intercalibration exercise and repealing Commission Decision 2013/480/EU. *Official Journal of the European Communities*, L47: 1-91.
- European Commission Directorate-General for Communications Networks, C., and T., (2021). Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the council Laying Down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and Amending Certain Union Legislative Acts. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021PC0206>.
- European Commission, 2022. Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and the Council on nature restoration. Brussels, 22.6.2022, COM(2022) 304 final, 2022/0195 (COD).
- Fernandes-Salvador, J. A., Davidson, K., Sourisseau, M., Revilla, M., Schmidt, W., Clarke, D., ... Silke, J. (2021). Current status of forecasting toxic harmful algae for the North-East Atlantic shellfish aquaculture industry. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8, 666583.
- Ferrari, R., Bryson, M., Bridge, T., Hustache, J., Williams, S. B., Byrne, M., Figueira, W. (2016). Quantifying the response of structural complexity and community composition to environmental change in marine communities. *Global change biology*, 22(5), 1965-1975.
- Ferrari, R., Malcolm, H. A., Byrne, M., Friedman, A., Williams, S. B., Schultz, A., ... Figueira, W. F. (2018). Habitat structural complexity metrics improve predictions of fish abundance and distribution. *Ecography*, 41(7), 1077-1091.
- Fernandes, J. A., Irigoien, X., Boyra, G., Lozano, J. A., Inza, I. (2009). Optimizing the number of classes in automated zooplankton classification. *Journal of Plankton Research*, 31(1), 19-29.
- Fernandes, J. A., Irigoien, X., Goikoetxea, N., Lozano, J. A., Inza, I., Pérez, A., Bode, A. (2010). Fish recruitment prediction, using robust supervised classification methods. *Ecological Modelling*, 221(2), 338-352.

- Fernandes, J. A., Kauppila, P., Uusitalo, L., Fleming-Lehtinen, V., Kuikka, S., Pitkänen, H. (2012). Evaluation of reaching the targets of the Water Framework Directive in the Gulf of Finland. *Environmental science & technology*, 46(15), 8220-8228.
- Fernandes, J. A., Irigoien, X., Lozano, J. A., Inza, I., Goikoetxea, N., Pérez, A. (2015). Evaluating machine-learning techniques for recruitment forecasting of seven North East Atlantic fish species. *Ecological Informatics*, 25, 35-42.
- Fernandes, J. A., Lozano, J. A., Inza, I., Irigoien, X., Pérez, A., Rodríguez, J. D. (2013). Supervised pre-processing approaches in multiple class variables classification for fish recruitment forecasting. *Environmental modelling & software*, 40, 245-254.
- Fernandes, J. A., Papathanasopoulou, E., Hattam, C., Queirós, A. M., Cheung, W. W., Yool, A., ... Barange, M. (2017). Estimating the ecological, economic and social impacts of ocean acidification and warming on UK fisheries. *Fish and Fisheries*, 18(3), 389-411.
- Fernandes, J. A., Rutterford, L., Simpson, S. D., Butenschön, M., Frölicher, T. L., Yool, A., ... & Grant, A. (2020a). Can we project changes in 31 fish abundance and distribution in response to climate?. *Global change biology*, 26(7), 3891-3905.
- Fernandes, J. A., Frölicher, T. L., Rutterford, L. A., Erauskin-Extramiana, M., & Cheung, W. W. (2020b). Changes of potential catches for North-East Atlantic small pelagic fisheries under climate change scenarios. *Regional environmental change*, 20, 1-16.
- Fernandes-Salvador, J. A., Davidson, K., Sourisseau, M., Revilla, M., Schmidt, W., Clarke, D., ... Silke, J. (2021). Current status of forecasting toxic harmful algae for the North-East Atlantic shellfish aquaculture industry. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8, 666583.
- Fernandes-Salvador, J. A., Goienetxea, I., Ibaibarriaga, L., Aranda, M., Cuende, E., Giuseppe, F. O. T. I., ... Caballero, A. (2022). Research for PECH Committee: Artificial Intelligence and the fisheries sector. www.doi.org/10.2861/73456
- Fjeld J., Achten, N., Hillgoss H., Nagy, A., Sriksumar, M. (2020) Principled Artificial Intelligence: Mapping Consensus in Ethical and Rights-Based Approaches to Principles for AI SSRN Electronic Journal 10.2139/SSRN.3518482
- Flores Júnior, R., Barbosa, C. C. F., Maciel, D. A., Novo, E. M. L. de M., Martins, V. S., Lobo, F. de L., Sander de Carvalho, L. A., Carlos, F. M. (2022). Hybrid Semi-Analytical Algorithm for Estimating Chlorophyll-A Concentration in Lower Amazon Floodplain Waters. *Frontiers in Remote Sensing*, 3.
- Fragkopoulou, E., Serrão, E. A., De Clerck, O., Costello, M. J., Araújo, M. B., Duarte, C. M., ... & Assis, J. (2022). Global biodiversity patterns of marine forests of brown macroalgae. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 31(4), 636-648.
- Francis, R. C. (2006). Measuring the strength of environment–recruitment relationships: the importance of including predictor screening within cross-validations. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 63(4), 594-599.
- Friedman, A., Pizarro, O., Williams, S. B., Johnson-Roberson, M. (2012). Multi-scale measures of rugosity, slope and aspect from benthic stereo image reconstructions. *PloS one*, 7(12), e50440.
- Frühe, L.; Cordier, T.; Dully, V.; Breiner, H.-W.; Lentendu, G.; Pawlowski, J.; Martins, C.; Wilding, T. A. Stoeck, T. (2020), 'Supervised machine learning is superior to indicator value inference in monitoring the environmental impacts of salmon aquaculture using eDNA metabarcodes', *Molecular Ecology*
- Galloway, A., Brunet, D., Valipour, R., McCusker, M., Biberhofer, J., Sobol, M. K., ... Taylor, G. W. (2022). Predicting dreissenid mussel abundance in nearshore waters using underwater imagery and deep learning. *Limnology and Oceanography: Methods*, 20(4), 233-248.
- Garcia, S., Herrera, F. (2008). An Extension on " Statistical Comparisons of Classifiers over Multiple Data Sets" for all Pairwise Comparisons. *Journal of machine learning research*, 9(12).
- Garmendia, J. M., Rodríguez, J. G., Borja, Á., Pouso, S., del Campo, A., Galparsoro, I., Fernandes-Salvador, J. A. (2023). Restoring seagrass meadows in Basque estuaries: nature-based solution for successful management. *Nature-Based Solutions*, 4, 100084.
- Gauci, A., Deidun, A., Abela, J., & Zarb Adami, K. (2016). Machine Learning for benthic sand and maerl classification and coverage estimation in coastal areas around the Maltese Islands. *Journal of applied research and technology*, 14(5), 338-344.
- Ghosh, A., Sufian, A., Sultana, F., Chakrabarti, A., De, D. (2020). Fundamental concepts of convolutional neural network. Recent trends and advances in artificial intelligence and Internet of Things, 519-567.
- Girshick, R., Donahue, J., Darrell, T., & Malik, J. (2014). Rich feature hierarchies for accurate object detection and semantic segmentation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (pp. 580-587).
- Granado, I., Hernando, L., Uriondo, Z., Fernandes-Salvador, J. A. (2024). A fishing route optimization decision support system: The case of the tuna purse seiner. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 312(2), 718-732.

- Gregor, I.; DrÄ¶fge, J.; Schirmer, M.; Quince, C. McHardy, A. C. (2016), 'PhyloPythiaS+: a self-training method for the rapid reconstruction of low-ranking taxonomic bins from metagenomes', *PeerJ* 4, e1603.
- Grandremy, N., Dupuy, C., Petitgas, P., Mestre, S. L., Bourriau, P., Nowaczyk, A., ... Romagnan, J. B. (2023). The ZooScan and the ZooCAM zooplankton imaging systems are intercomparable: A benchmark on the Bay of Biscay zooplankton. *Limnology and Oceanography: Methods*, 21(11), 718-733.
- Hartmann, M., Hosack, G. R., Hillary, R. M., & Vanhatalo, J. (2017). Gaussian process framework for temporal dependence and discrepancy functions in Ricker-type population growth models. *Annals of Applied Statistics*, 11(3): 1375-1402.
- Hill, P. R., Kumar, A., Temimi, M., Bull, D. R. (2020). HABNet: Machine learning, remote sensing-based detection of harmful algal blooms. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, 13, 3229-3239.
- Höschle, C., Cubaynes, H. C., Clarke, P. J., Humphries, G., Borowicz, A. (2021). The Potential of Satellite Imagery for Surveying Whales. *Sensors (Basel, Switzerland)*, 21(3), 963. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21030963>
- HELCOM 2012. HELCOM Baltic Sea Action Plan – 2021 update. <https://helcom.fi/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/Baltic-Sea-Action-Plan-2021-update.pdf>
- Huber, R., D'Onofrio, C., Devaraju, A., Klump, J., Loescher, H. W., Kindermann, S., Guru, S., Grant, M., Morris, B., Wyborn, L., Evans, B., Goldfarb, D., Genazzio, M. A., Ren, X., Magagna, Jacobsen, A., Azevedo, R. de M., Juty, N., Batista, D., Coles, S., Cornet, R., Courtot, M., Crosas, M., Dumontier, M., Evelo, C. T., Goble, C., Guizzardi, G., Hansen, K. K., Hasnain, A., Hettne, K., Heringa, J., Hooft, R. W. W., Imming, M., Jeffery, K. G., ... Schultes, E. (2020). Fair principles: Interpretations and implementation considerations. In *Data Intelligence (Vol. 2, Issues 1–2, pp. 10–29)*. MIT Press Journals.
- Huby, A., R. Sagban R. Alubady, "Oil Spill Detection based on Machine Learning and Deep Learning: A Review," 2022 5th International Conference on Engineering Technology and its Applications (IICETA), Al-Najaf, Iraq, 2022, pp. 85-90, doi: 10.1109/IICETA54559.2022.9888651.
- Irigoien, X., Fernandes, J. A., Grosjean, P., Denis, K., Albaina, A., Santos, M. (2009). Spring zooplankton distribution in the Bay of Biscay from 1998 to 2006 in relation with anchovy recruitment. *Journal of plankton research*, 31(1), 1-17.
- Jalal, A., Salman, A., Mian, A., Shortis, M., Shafait, F. (2020). Fish detection and species classification in underwater environments using deep learning with temporal information. *Ecological Informatics*, 57, 101088.
- Janga, B., Asamani, G., Sun, Z., Cristea, N. (2023). A Review of Practical AI for Remote Sensing in Earth Sciences. *Remote Sensing*, 15(16), 4112.
- Jetz, W., McGeoch, M. A., Guralnick, R., Ferrier, S., Beck, J., Costello, M. J., ... Turak, E. (2019). Essential biodiversity variables for mapping and monitoring species populations. *Nature ecology & evolution*, 3(4), 539-551.
- Jia, T., Kapelan, Z., de Vries, R., Vriend, P., Peereboom, E. C., Okkerman, I., Taormina, R. (2023). Deep learning for detecting macroplastic litter in water bodies: A review. *Water Research*, 231, 119632. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2023.119632>
- Joshi, I. D., Stramski, D., Reynolds, R. A., Robinson, D. H. (2023). Performance assessment and validation of ocean color sensor-specific algorithms for estimating the concentration of particulate organic carbon in oceanic surface waters from satellite observations. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 286, 113417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2022.113417>
- Keck, F., Brantschen, J., & Altermatt, F. (2023). A combination of machine-learning and eDNA reveals the genetic signature of environmental change at the landscape levels. *Molecular Ecology*, 32(17), 4791-4800.
- Kettunen, J., Mehtätalo, L., Tuittila, E. S., Korrensalo, A., & Vanhatalo, J. (2023). Joint Species Distribution Modeling of Percentage Cover Data with Exclusive Competition for Space. *Environmetrics*, e2830.
- Kikaki K, Kakogeorgiou I, Mikeli P, Raitos DE, Karantzalos K (2022) MARIDA: A benchmark for Marine Debris detection from Sentinel-2 remote sensing data. *PLoS ONE* 17(1): e0262247. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0262247>
- Kinkade, D., Shepherd, A. (2022). Geoscience data publication: Practices and perspectives on enabling the FAIR guiding principles. *Geoscience Data Journal*, 9(1), 177-186.
- Kissling, W. D., Ahumada, J. A., Bowser, A., Fernandez, M., Fernández, N., García, E. A., ... Hardisty, A. R. (2018). Building essential biodiversity variables (EBV s) of species distribution and abundance at a global scale. *Biological reviews*, 93(1), 600-625.
- Kotsiantis, S. B., Kanellopoulos, D., Pintelas, P. E. (2006). Data preprocessing for supervised learning. *International journal of computer science*, 1(2), 111-117.
- Kotsiantis, S. B., Zaharakis, I., Pintelas, P. (2007). Supervised machine learning: A review of classification techniques. *Emerging artificial intelligence applications in computer engineering*, 160(1), 3-24.

- Kotta, J., Kutser, T., Teeveer, K., Vahtmäe, E., & Pärnoja, M. (2013). Predicting species cover of marine macrophyte and invertebrate species combining hyperspectral remote sensing, machine learning and regression techniques. *PLoS One*, 8(6), e63946.
- Kotta, J., Vanhatalo, J., Jänes, H., Orav-Kotta, H., Rugiu, L., Jormalainen, V., ... & Johannesson, K. (2019). Integrating experimental and distribution data to predict future species patterns. *Scientific reports*, 9(1), 1821.
- Krag, L. A., Madsen, N., & Karlsen, J. D. (2009). A study of fish behaviour in the extension of a demersal trawl using a multi-compartment separator frame and SIT camera system. *Fisheries Research*, 98(1-3), 62-66.
- Kraft, K., Velhonoja, O., Eerola, T., Suikkanen, S., Tamminen, T., Haraguchi, L., ... & Seppälä, J. (2022). Towards operational phytoplankton recognition with automated high-throughput imaging, near-real-time data processing, and convolutional neural networks. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9, 867695.
- Krinitzkiy, M., Sprygin, A., Elizarov, S., Narizhnaya, A., Shikhov, A., Chernokulsky, A. (2023). Towards the Accurate Automatic Detection of Mesoscale Convective Systems in Remote Sensing Data: From Data Mining to Deep Learning Models and Their Applications. *Remote Sensing*, 15(14), 3493. MDPI AG. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs15143493>
- Lachenbruch, P.A., Mickey, M.R., 1968. Estimation of error rates in discriminant analysis. *Technometrics* 10, 1–11.
- Lanzén, A.; Mendibil, I.; Borja, Á. Alonso-Sáez, L. (2021), 'A microbial mandala for environmental monitoring – predicting multiple impacts on estuarine prokaryote communities of the Bay of Biscay', *Molecular Ecology* 30, 2969–2987.
- Larson, S. C. (1931). The shrinkage of the coefficient of multiple correlation. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 22(1), 45.
- Lathrop, R. G., Merchant, D., Niles, L., Paludo, D., Santos, C. D., Larrain, C. E., Feigin, S., et al. (2022). Multi-Sensor Remote Sensing of Intertidal Flat Habitats for Migratory Shorebird Conservation. *Remote Sensing*, 14(19), 5016. MDPI AG. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs14195016>
- Lekunberri, X., Ruiz, J., Quincoces, I., Dornaika, F., Arganda-Carreras, I., Fernandes, J. A. (2022). Identification and measurement of tropical tuna species in purse seiner catches using computer vision and deep learning. *Ecological Informatics*, 67, 101495.
- Li, X., Liu, B., Zheng, G., Ren, Y., Zhang, S., Liu, Y., Gao, L., Liu, Y., Zhang, B., Wang, F. (2020). Deep-learning-based information mining from ocean remote-sensing imagery. *National Science Review*, 7(10), 1584–1605.
- Li, X.; Li, F.; Min, X.; Xie, Y.; Zhang, Y. 2023. Embracing eDNA and machine learning for taxonomy-free microorganisms biomonitoring to assess the river ecological status. *Ecological Indicators* 155, 110948. doi: 10.1016/j.ecolind.2023.110948.
- Libbrecht, M. W. Noble, W. S. (2015), 'Machine learning applications in genetics and genomics', *Nature Reviews Genetics* 16, 321
- Liu, Y., Zheng, Q., Li, X. (2023). Detection and Analysis of Mesoscale Eddies Based on Deep Learning. In X. Li & F. Wang (Eds.), *Artificial Intelligence Oceanography* (pp. 209–225). Springer Nature. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-6375-9_10
- Lucas, T.C.D. (2020). A translucent box: interpretable machine learning in ecology. *Ecological Monographs*, 90, e01422.
- Luo, J. Y., Irisson, J. O., Graham, B., Guigand, C., Sarafraz, A., Mader, C., Cowen, R. K. (2018). Automated plankton image analysis using convolutional neural networks. *Limnology and Oceanography: methods*, 16(12), 814-827.
- Marquez, L., Fragkopoulou, E., Cavanaugh, K. C., Houskeeper, H. F., & Assis, J. (2022). Artificial intelligence convolutional neural networks map giant kelp forests from satellite imagery. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1), 22196.
- Miloslavich, P., N. J. Bax, S. E. Simmons, E. Klein, W. Appeltans, O. Aburto-Oropeza, M. A. Garcia, S. D. Batten, L. Benedetti-Cecchi, D. M. Checkley, S. Chiba, J. E. Duffy, D. C. Dunn, A. Fischer, J. Gunn, R. Kudela, F. Marsac, F. E. Muller-Karger, D. Obura, Y.-J. Shin, 2018. Essential ocean variables for global sustained observations of biodiversity and ecosystem changes. *Global Change Biology*, 24: 2416-2433.
- Mohamed, H., Nadaoka, K., & Nakamura, T. (2018). Assessment of machine learning algorithms for automatic benthic cover monitoring and mapping using towed underwater video camera and high-resolution satellite images. *Remote Sensing*, 10(5), 773.
- Montanyès, M., Weigel, B., & Lindegren, M. (2023). Community assembly processes and drivers shaping marine fish community structure in the North Sea. *Ecography*, 2023(10), e06642.
- Mons, B., Neylon, C., Velterop, J., Dumontier, M., da Silva Santos, L. O. B., Wilkinson, M. D. (2017). Cloudy, increasingly FAIR; revisiting the FAIR Data guiding principles for the European Open Science Cloud. *Information Services & Use*, 37(1), 49-56.

- Mosteller, F., Tukey, J.F., 1968. Data analysis, including statistics. In: Lindzey, G., Aronson, E. (Eds.), *Handbook of Social Psychology*, vol. II. Addison-Wesley, Reading, MA, p. 588.
- Murillas-Maza, A., Broszeit, S., Pouso, S., Bueno-Pardo, J., Ruiz-Frau, A., Terrados, J., ... Fernandes-Salvador, J. A. (2023). Ecosystem indicators to measure the effectiveness of marine nature-based solutions on society and biodiversity under climate change. *Nature-Based Solutions*, 100085.
- Nadeau, C., Bengio, Y., 2003. Inference for the generalization error. *Machine Learning*, 52 (3), 239–281.
- Norberg, A., Abrego, N., Blanchet, F. G., Adler, F. R., Anderson, B. J., Anttila, J., ... & Ovaskainen, O. (2019). A comprehensive evaluation of predictive performance of 33 species distribution models at species and community levels. *Ecological monographs*, 89(3), e01370.
- Nur Korkmaz, B., Diamant, R., Danino, G., & Testolin, A. (2023). Automated detection of dolphin whistles with convolutional networks and transfer learning. *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence*, 6, 1099022.
- Ovaskainen, O., Tikhonov, G., Norberg, A., Guillaume Blanchet, F., Duan, L., Dunson, D., ... & Abrego, N. (2017). How to make more out of community data? A conceptual framework and its implementation as models and software. *Ecology letters*, 20(5), 561-576.
- Palomares, I., Martínez-Cámara, E., Montes, R., García-Moral, P., Chiachio, M., Chiachio, J., ... Herrera, F. (2021). A panoramic view and swot analysis of artificial intelligence for achieving the sustainable development goals by 2030: progress and prospects. *Applied Intelligence*, 51(9), 6497-6527.
- Park, K.-A., Woo, H.-J., Lee, E.-Y. (2020). The application of a hybrid sea surface temperature algorithm to COMS geostationary satellite data in the Northwest Pacific Ocean. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 41(15), 5953–5973.
- Peltonen, H., & Weigel, B. (2022). Responses of coastal fishery resources to rapid environmental changes. *Journal of Fish Biology*, 101(3), 686-698.
- Pereira, H. M., Ferrier, S., Walters, M., Geller, G. N., Jongman, R. H., Scholes, R. J., ... Wegmann, M. (2013). Essential biodiversity variables. *Science*, 339(6117), 277-278.
- Pollicelli, D., Coscarella, M., Delrieux, C. (2020). Rol detection and segmentation algorithms for marine mammals photo-identification. *Ecological Informatics*, 56, 101038.
- Probst, W. N. 2020. How emerging data technologies can increase trust and transparency in fisheries. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 77: 1286–1294.
- Pucino, N., Kennedy, D. M., Young, M., Ierodiaconou, D. (2022). Assessing the accuracy of Sentinel-2 instantaneous subpixel shorelines using synchronous UAV ground truth surveys. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 282, 113293.
- Queirós, A. M., Fernandes, J. A., Faulwetter, S., Nunes, J., Rastrick, S. P., Mieszkowska, N., ... Widdicombe, S. (2015). Scaling up experimental ocean acidification and warming research: from individuals to the ecosystem. *Global change biology*, 21(1), 130-143.
- Reunanen, J. (2003). Overfitting in making comparisons between variable selection methods. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 3(Mar), 1371-1382.
- Roberts, D. R., Bahn, V., Ciuti, S., Boyce, M. S., Elith, J., Guillera-Aroita, G., ... & Dormann, C. F. (2017). Cross-validation strategies for data with temporal, spatial, hierarchical, or phylogenetic structure. *Ecography*, 40(8), 913-929.
- Rodríguez, J.D., Pérez, A., Lozano, J.A., 2009. A sensitivity study of bias and variance of k-fold cross-validation in prediction error estimation. Technical Report EHUKZAA-1K-1/09. University of the Basque Country, February.
- Rosen, S., Holst, J. C. 2013. DeepVision in-trawl imaging: Sampling the water column in four dimensions. *Fisheries Research*, 148: 64–73.
- Rubbens, P., Brodie, S., Cordier, T., Destro Barcellos, D., Devos, P., Fernandes-Salvador, J. A., ... Irisson, J. O. (2023). Machine learning in marine ecology: an overview of techniques and applications. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 80(7), 1829-1853.
- Ryabov, A., Blasius, B., Hillebrand, H., Olenina, I. Gross, T. (2022). Estimation of functional diversity and species traits from ecological monitoring data. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 119, e2118156119.
- Sagi, T., Lehahn, Y., Bar, K. (2020). Artificial intelligence for ocean science data integration: current state, gaps, and way forward. *Elem Sci Anth*, 8, 21. <https://doi.org/10.1525/elementa.418>
- Salerno E., Di Paola C., Lo Duca A., (Eds) (2023) Remote Sensing for Maritime Monitoring and Vessel Identification. [Special issue]. *Remote Sensing* (ISSN 2072-4292). https://www.mdpi.com/journal/remotesensing/special_issues/493C7J6D51#info
- Sarafanov, M., Kazakov, E., Nikitin, N. O., Kalyuzhnaya, A. V. (2020). A Machine Learning Approach for Remote Sensing Data Gap-Filling with Open-Source Implementation: An Example Regarding Land Surface

- Temperature, Surface Albedo and NDVI. *Remote Sensing*, 12(23), 3865. MDPI AG. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs12233865>
- Schenone, S., Azhar, M., Ramírez, C. A. V., Strozzi, A. G., Delmas, P., Thrush, S. F. (2021). Mapping the delivery of ecological functions combining field collected data and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs). *Ecosystems*, 1-12.
- Schirripa, M. J., Colbert, J. J. (2006). Interannual changes in sablefish (*Anoplopoma fimbria*) recruitment in relation to oceanographic conditions within the California Current System. *Fisheries Oceanography*, 15(1), 25-36.
- Schmidt, S., Maudire, G., Nys, C., Sudre, J., Harscoat, V., Dibarboure, G., Huynh, F. (2020). Streamlining data and service centers for easier access to data and analytical services: The strategy of ODATIS as the gateway to French marine data. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 7, 548126.
- Schmeller, D. S., Mihoub, J. B., Bowser, A., Arvanitidis, C., Costello, M. J., Fernandez, M., ... Isaac, N. J. (2017). An operational definition of essential biodiversity variables. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 26, 2967-2972.
- Schoening, T., Durden, J. M., Faber, C., Felden, J., Heger, K., Hoving, H. J. T., ... Zurowietz, M. (2022). Making marine image data FAIR. *Scientific data*, 9(1), 414.
- Schröder, S. M., Kiko, R., Koch, R. (2020). MorphoCluster: Efficient annotation of plankton images by clustering. *Sensors*, 20(11), 3060.
- Silva, B., Mestre, F., Barreiro, S., Alves, P. J., & Herrera, J. M. (2022). *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 13: 2356-2362.
- Singh, P. K., Sarkar, R., Nasipuri, M. (2015). Statistical validation of multiple classifiers over multiple datasets in the field of pattern recognition. *International Journal of Applied Pattern Recognition*, 2(1), 1-23.
- Snaveley, N., Seitz, S. M., Szeliski, R. (2006). Photo tourism: exploring photo collections in 3D. In *ACM siggraph 2006 papers* (pp. 835-846).
- Sohns, A., Hickey, G. M., Temby, O. (2022). Exploring the potential impacts of machine learning on trust in fishery management. *Fish and Fisheries*, 23(4), 1016-1023.
- Soldi, G., Gaglione, D., Forti, N., Millefiori, L. M., Braca, P., Carniel, S., Simone, A. D., Iodice, A., Riccio, D., Daffinà, F. C., Quattrociochi, D., Bottini, G., Willett, P., Farina, A. (2021). Space-Based Global Maritime Surveillance. Part II: Artificial Intelligence and Data Fusion Techniques. *IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine*, 36(9), 30–42.
- Sosik, H. M., & Olson, R. J. (2007). Automated taxonomic classification of phytoplankton sampled with imaging-in-flow cytometry. *Limnology and Oceanography: Methods*, 5(6), 204-216.
- Staehr, S. U., Van der Zande, D., Staehr, P. A. U., Markager, S. (2022). Suitability of multisensory satellites for long-term chlorophyll assessment in coastal waters: A case study in optically complex waters of the temperate region. *Ecological Indicators*, 134, 108479. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2021.108479>
- Statnikov, A., Aliferis, C. F., Tsamardinos, I., Hardin, D., Levy, S. (2005). A comprehensive evaluation of multicategory classification methods for microarray gene expression cancer diagnosis. *Bioinformatics*, 21(5), 631-643.
- Stock, A., Subramaniam, A., Van Dijken, G. L., Wedding, L. M., Arrigo, K. R., Mills, M. M., Cameron, M. A., et al. (2020). Comparison of Cloud-Filling Algorithms for Marine Satellite Data. *Remote Sensing*, 12(20), 3313. MDPI AG. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs12203313>
- Stramski, D., Joshi, I., Reynolds, R. A. (2022). Ocean color algorithms to estimate the concentration of particulate organic carbon in surface waters of the global ocean in support of a long-term data record from multiple satellite missions. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 269, 112776.
- Sun, W., Nasraoui, O., Shafto, P. (2020). Evolution and impact of bias in human and machine learning algorithm interaction. *Plos one*, 15(8), e0235502.
- Taconet, M., Kroodsma, D., Fernandes, J. A. (2019). Global Atlas of AIS-based fishing activity—Challenges and opportunities. Rome, FAO. <https://www.fao.org/publications/card/es/c/CA7012EN/>
- Tanhua, T., Pouliquen, S., Hausman, J., O'brien, K., Bricher, P., De Bruin, T., ... Zhao, Z. (2019). Ocean FAIR data services. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 6, 440. Traganos, D., Lee, C. B., Blume, A., Poursanidis, D., Čizmek, H., Deter, J., Mačić, V., MontefalconeM., Pergent, G., Pergent-Martini, C. (2022). Spatially explicit seagrass extent mapping across the entire Mediterranean. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9.
- Tredennick, A.T., Hooker, G., Ellner, S.P. Adler, P.B. (2021). A practical guide to selecting models for exploration, inference, and prediction in ecology. *Ecology*, 102, e03336.
- Tseng, C.-H., Kuo, Y.-F. 2020. Detecting and counting harvested fish and identifying fish types in electronic monitoring system videos using deep convolutional neural networks. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 77: 1367–1378.
- Tsiakos, C.-A. D., Chalkias, C. (2023). Use of Machine Learning and Remote Sensing Techniques for Shoreline Monitoring: A Review of Recent Literature. *Applied Sciences*, 13(5), 3268.

- Uranga, J., Arrizabalaga, H., Boyra, G., Hernandez, M. C., Goñi, N., Arregui, I., Fernandes, J. A., et al. 2017. Detecting the presence-absence of bluefin tuna by automated analysis of medium-range sonars on fishing vessels. *PLOS ONE*, 12: e0171382.
- Urban, M. C. et al. Improving the forecast for biodiversity under climate change. *Science* 353, 6304, aad8466 (2016).
- Uusitalo, L. (2007). Advantages and challenges of Bayesian networks in environmental modelling. *Ecological modelling*, 203(3-4), 312-318.
- Uusitalo, L., Fernandes, J. A., Bachiller, E., Tasala, S., Lehtiniemi, M. (2016). Semi-automated classification method addressing marine strategy framework directive (MSFD) zooplankton indicators. *Ecological indicators*, 71, 398-405.
- Vahtmäe, E.; Kotta, J.; Argus, L.; Kotta, M.; Kotta, I.; Kutser, T. 2022. A model-based assessment of canopy scale primary productivity for the Baltic Sea benthic vegetation using environmental variables and spectral indices. *Remote Sensing*, 14, 158.
- Valdez, J. W., Callaghan, C. T., Junker, J., Purvis, A., Hill, S. L., Pereira, H. M. (2023). The undetectability of global biodiversity trends using local species richness. *Ecography*, 2023(3), e06604.
- Vanhatalo, J., Veneranta, L., & Hudd, R. (2012). Species distribution modeling with Gaussian processes: A case study with the youngest stages of sea spawning whitefish (*Coregonus lavaretus* L. sl) larvae. *Ecological Modelling*, 228, 49-58.
- Vanhatalo, J., Hartmann, M., & Veneranta, L. (2020). Additive multivariate Gaussian processes for joint species distribution modeling with heterogeneous data. *Bayesian Analysis*, 15(2):415-447.
- Vasconcelos, R. N., Lima, A. T. C., Lentini, C. A. D., Miranda, J. G. V., de Mendonça, L. F. F., Lopes, J. M., Santana, M. M. M., et al. (2023). Deep Learning-Based Approaches for Oil Spill Detection: A Bibliometric Review of Research Trends and Challenges. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 11(7), 1406. MDPI AG. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/jmse11071406>
- Veale, M., Binns, R., Edwards, L. 2018. Algorithms that remember: model inversion attacks and data protection law. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 376: 20180083. Royal Society.
- Vehtari, A., & Ojanen, J. (2012). A survey of Bayesian predictive methods for model assessment, selection and comparison. *Statistics Surveys*, 8 (2014), 1-1.
- Villon, S., Chaumont, M., Subsol, G., Villéger, S., Claverie, T., Mouillot, D. (2016, October). Coral reef fish detection and recognition in underwater videos by supervised machine learning: Comparison between Deep Learning and HOG+ SVM methods. In *International Conference on Advanced Concepts for Intelligent Vision Systems* (pp. 160-171). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Vinuesa, R., Azizpour, H., Leite, I., Balaam, M., Dignum, V., Domisch, S., ... Fuso Nerini, F. (2020). The role of artificial intelligence in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. *Nature communications*, 11(1), 1-10.
- Walton, R., Dixon, A., Kaye, S., Outhwaite, O., Agnesi, S., Marin, O., Mo, G., Ojaveer, H., Ounanian, K., McOwen, C., Papadopoulou, N., Smith, C., Thornton, H., Todorova, V., van Noort, C., Venancio, M., 2023. OBAMA-NEXT Deliverable 6.1. Review, analysis and crosswalk of the data requirements of key policies. 42 pp.
- Wang, D., Shao, Q., Yue, H. (2019). Surveying Wild Animals from Satellites, Manned Aircraft and Unmanned Aerial Systems (UASs): A Review. *Remote Sensing*, 11(11), 1308. MDPI AG. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs11111308>
- Wang, M., Wang, D., Xiang, Y., Liang, Y., Xia, R., Yang, J., Xu, F., Huang, X. (2023). Fusion of ocean data from multiple sources using deep learning: Utilizing sea temperature as an example. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 10.
- Weigel, B., Mäkinen, J., Kallasvuori, M., & Vanhatalo, J. (2021). Exposing changing phenology of fish larvae by modeling climate effects on temporal early life-stage shifts. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 666, 135-148.
- Weimann, A.; Mooren, K.; Frank, J.; Pope, P. B.; Bremges, A. McHardy, A. C. (2016), 'From Genomes to Phenotypes: TraitAr, the Microbial Trait Analyzer', *mSystems* 1(6).
- Wen, Q., Sun, L., Yang, F., Song, X., Gao, J., Wang, X., Xu, H. (2021). Time Series Data Augmentation for Deep Learning: A Survey. In: *Proceedings of the Thirtieth International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence*. pp. 4653–4660.
- Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., ... Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific data*, 3(1), 1-9.
- Willassen, E., J.-I. Westgaard, J. A. Kongsrud, T. Hanebrikke, P. Buhl-Mortensen, B. Holte, 2022. Benthic invertebrates in Svalbard fjords—when metabarcoding does not outperform traditional biodiversity assessment. *PeerJ*, 10: e14321.

- Wilson, K. L., Wong, M. C., Devred, E. (2020). Branching Algorithm to Identify Bottom Habitat in the Optically Complex Coastal Waters of Atlantic Canada Using Sentinel-2 Satellite Imagery. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 8.
- Zarauz, L., Irigoien, X., Fernandes, J. A. (2009). Changes in plankton size structure and composition, during the generation of a phytoplankton bloom, in the central Cantabrian sea. *Journal of plankton research*, 31(2), 193-207.
- Zhang, S., Zhang, C., Yang, Q. (2003). Data preparation for data mining. *Applied artificial intelligence*, 17(5-6), 375-381.

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